

**The Effect of *Parthenium Hysterophorus* Weed on Basin
Hydrology**

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Certificate

It is certified that the work done in this thesis entitled “The Effect of *Parthenium Hysterophorus* Weed on Basin Hydrology” by Mr. Soham Adla (Y9227589) has been carried out under my supervision in the partial fulfillment of the award of the degree of Master of Technology in Civil Engineering from the Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, and that this work has not been submitted elsewhere for a degree.

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Abstract

Parthenium hysterophorus weed is an invasive noxious weed with a high growth rate and spread which can be attributed to its adaptability to a variety of soil types and climatic conditions. Its hazardous impacts on human health, livestock and agricultural crops have been documented, and so have the mechanical, cultural, chemical and biological techniques of its control. However, few studies have investigated possible impacts of *Parthenium* on the hydrology of a river basin, either qualitatively or quantitatively. This study aimed to quantify the effect of a *Parthenium* invasion on water balance components at a river basin scale. Laboratory experiments and Penman-Monteith Evapotranspiration modeling indicate that *Parthenium* has lower evapotranspiration losses as compared to reference grasses and agricultural crops. SWAT modeling of a *Parthenium* invasion of the Punpun river basin re-establishes the tendency of *Parthenium* to transpire less, except during soil stressed conditions where *Parthenium* infested soil has a reduced moisture loss, which leads to a short period of higher evapotranspiration compared to agricultural land cover just before the onset of monsoons. Further, the modeling results suggest that *Parthenium* invasion does not have a significant effect on surface discharge and groundwater recharge at a basin scale. The thesis highlights the lack of data on the physiology of *Parthenium* which is needed to understand its impact on the hydrology of a basin. Lysimeter experiments under control environment are recommended to overcome some of the existing gaps in our present understanding of *Parthenium*.

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List of Acronyms

AGRL – Agricultural Land Generic (land cover nomenclature)

APHRODITE – Asian Precipitation: Highly Resolved Observational Data Integration Towards Evaluation (of Water Resources)

ARS – Agricultural Research Service

ASCE – American Society of Civil Engineers

CN – Curve Number

CREAMS - Chemicals, Runoff and Erosion from Agricultural Management Systems

DEM – Digital Elevation Model

DWSM – Dynamic Watershed Simulation Model

EPIC - Environment Impact Policy Climate

ESRI – Environmental Systems Research Institute

ET – Evapotranspiration

GIS – Geographical Information System

GLEAMS - Groundwater Loading Effects on Agricultural Management Systems

GPS – Global Positioning System

GRBMP – Ganga River Basin Management Plan

HRU – Hydrologic Response Unit

HSPF – Hydrologic Simulation Program - Fortran

IAS – Invasive Alien Species

ISRO – Indian Space Research Organisation

LAI – Leaf Area Index

LHS – Left Hand Side

NBSS – National Bureau of Soil Survey

NRSC – National Remote Sensing Centre

PET – Potential Evapotranspiration

PM – Penman-Monteith

PRTH – *Parthenium* (used as land cover nomenclature)

RHS – Right Hand Side

SUFI-2 – Sequential Uncertainty and Fitting Version 2

SWAT – Soil and Water Assessment Tool

SWAT – Soil and Water Assessment Tool

SWAT-CUP – Soil and Water Assessment Tool Calibration and Uncertainty Procedures

SWRRB - Simulator for Water Resources in Rural Basins

US – United States (of America)

USDA – United States Department of Agriculture

List of Symbols

Δ = slope of the saturation vapor pressure-temperature relationship [KPa/ $^{\circ}$ C]

μ = specific yield of the (shallow) aquifer [m/m]

aq_{sh} = water stored in shallow aquifer at the beginning of day i [mm]

$aq_{shthr,q}$ = threshold water level in shallow aquifer for groundwater contribution to AWC_{ly} = available water capacity for layer ly [mm]

C_d = Denominator constant, changes according to reference type and time step [s/m]

CN = Curve number for a particular combination of soil permeability, land use and antecedent soil water conditions, calculated daily by SWAT

C_n = Numerator constant, changes according to reference type and time step [K mm s^3 /Mg/d or K mm s^3 /Mg/hr]

C_p = specific heat of the air [MJ/kg/ $^{\circ}$ C]

$c_{wv(air)}$ = concentration of water vapour in the air outside the leaf [mol/m 3]

$c_{wv(leaf)}$ = concentration of water vapour inside the air spaces within the leaf [mol/m 3]

$c_{wv(sat)}$ = saturation water vapour concentration [mol/m 3]

d = zero plane displacement height [m]

d_r = inverse relative distance factor (squared) for earth-sun [dimensionless]

$E'_{soil,ly}$ = evaporative demand for layer ly adjusted for water content [mm]

E''_s = maximum soil water evaporation during a given day [mm]

$E''_{soil,ly}$ = amount of water removed by evaporation from layer ly [mm]

e_a = actual vapor pressure of the air [kPa]

$E_{a,i}$ = evapotranspiration on the i th day [mm]

$epco$ = plant uptake compensation factor

e_s = saturation vapor pressure of the air [kPa]

$E_{soil,z}$ = evaporative demand at z depth [mm]

E_t = maximum plant transpiration on a given day, using Penman Monteith equation [mm]

$E_{t,act}$ = actual amount of daily transpiration [mm]

ET_{ref} = reference evapotranspiration [mm/d or mm/hr]

f_{cd} = cloudiness function [dimensionless]

FC_{ly} = water content at field capacity [mm]

G = soil heat flux [$\text{MJ}/\text{m}^2/\text{day}$ or $\text{MJ}/\text{m}^2/\text{hr}$]

G_{sc} = solar constant [$4.92 \text{ MJ}/\text{m}^2/\text{hr}$]

h = mean height of vegetation [m]

h_{wtbl} = height of the ground water table [m]

I_a = initial abstractions including surface storage, interception and infiltration prior to runoff [mm]

J = number of the day of the year between 1 and 365 or 366 (depending on whether the year of study is a leap year)

k = von Karman's constant = 0.41 [dimensionless]

k_{RS} = adjustment coefficient (0.16 for 'interior' locations where the local land mass dominates and no large body impacts air masses) [$^{\circ}\text{C}^{-0.5}$]

K_{sat} = hydraulic conductivity of the aquifer [mm/day]

K_{time} = units conversion [86400 s/d when ET_0 is in mm/d and 3600 s/hr when ET_0 in

L_{gw} = distance from the main channel to the sub-basin divide for the groundwater [mm/hr]

P = atmospheric pressure at the AWS [kPa]

$Q_{gw,i}$ = underground runoff during the i th day [mm]

Q_{surf} = accumulated runoff or rainfall excess [mm]

$Q_{surf,i}$ = surface runoff for the i th day [mm]

R = gas constant (=8.314 J/mol/K)

r_a = aerodynamic resistance [s/m]

R_a = Extraterrestrial radiation [$\text{MJ}/\text{m}^2/\text{d}$]

r_b = resistance of the boundary layer adjacent to the leaf [s/m]

$R_{day,i}$ = precipitation (including snowfall) for i th day [mm]

RH = relative humidity of the water vapour [dimensionless]

R_n = Net radiation [$\text{MJ}/\text{m}^2/\text{d}$]

R_n = net radiation [$\text{MJ}/\text{m}^2/\text{day}$ or $\text{MJ}/\text{m}^2/\text{hr}$]

R_{nl} = Net longwave radiation, defined as positive upwards [$\text{MJ}/\text{m}^2/\text{d}$]

R_{ns} = Net shortwave radiation, defined as positive downwards [$\text{MJ}/\text{m}^2/\text{d}$]

r_s = (bulk) surface resistance [s/m]

R_s = incoming shortwave radiation [$\text{MJ}/\text{m}^2/\text{d}$]

r_s = resistance at the stomatal pore [s/m]

R_{so} = calculated clear sky radiation [$\text{MJ}/\text{m}^2/\text{d}$]

S = retention parameter, a function of the land use, soil, slope and management, $\text{s}^3/\text{Mg}/\text{d}$ or $\text{K mm s}^3/\text{Mg}/\text{hr}$]

SW_{ly} = soil water content in the soil layer ly for a particular day [mm]

SW_o = soil moisture at the beginning of the time step [mm]

SW_t = soil moisture at time t [mm]

T = mean daily temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]

t = time of simulation [days]

T_{Kmax} = maximum absolute temperature during the day [K]

T_{Kmin} = minimum absolute temperature during the day [K]

T_{max} = maximum temperature during the day [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]

T_{min} = minimum temperature during the day [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]

u_2 = mean daily or hourly wind speed at 2 m height [m/s]

u_z = wind speed at height of z metres [m/s]

V_w = partial molar volume of liquid water

$w'_{up,ly}$ = adjusted daily potential water uptake for layer ly [mm]

$w''_{up,ly}$ = potential water uptake adjusted for initial soil water content [mm]

$w_{actualup}$ = total daily plant water uptake from all layers of the soil [mm]

$w_{actualup,ly}$ = actual daily water uptake from layer ly of the soil [mm]

w_{demand} = water uptake demand not met by the overlying layers [mm]

WP_{ly} = water content for layer ly , at wilting point [mm]

$w_{rchr,sh}$ = recharge entering shallow aquifer on i th day [mm]

$w_{seep,i}$ = seepage of water from the soil into deeper layers on the i th day [mm]

$w_{up,ly}$ = potential daily water uptake for layer ly [mm]

$w_{up,zl}$ = potential water uptake from the lower boundary of the soil layer [mm]

$w_{up,zu}$ = potential water uptake from the upper boundary of the soil layer [mm]

z = height of the AWS above mean sea level [m]

z_h = height of humidity and air temperature measurements [m]

z_{oh} = roughness length governing transfer of heat and vapour = $0.0123h$ [m]

z_{om} = roughness length governing momentum transfer = $0.123h$ [m]

z_{root} = depth of root development in the soil [mm]

z_w = height of wind measurements [m]

α = albedo or canopy reflection coefficient [dimensionless]

α_{gw} = baseflow recession constant

β_w = water-use distribution parameter

γ = psychrometric constant [kPa/°C]

δ = solar declination [radians]

λ = latent heat of vaporization [MJ/kg]

ρ_a = mean air density at constant pressure [kg/m³]

ρ_w = density of water [Mg/m³] taken as 1.0 Mg/m³

σ = Stefan-Boltzmann constant [4.901×10^{-9} MJ K⁻⁴ m⁻²/d]

φ = geographical latitude [radians]

ψ_w = water potential (a measure of free energy per unit volume) [J/m³]

ω_s = sunset hour angle [radians]

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Invasive Alien Species

Invasive alien species (IAS) are those species of plants, animals, fungi or microorganisms which on being introduced and/or having spread into regions beyond their natural habitat, threaten the biodiversity of the invaded region (YR 2009, 2010) . Only a small percentage of organisms which get transported to new environments become invasive, but over time, the accumulated negative impacts may substantially affect the habitats environmentally, economically and/or ecologically. For a species to become invasive starting from an initially low density existence, its growth parameters must surpass those of native species, it must spread in its new environment, increase in density, and be able to harm ecosystems within its range.

The common features of IAS are rapid growth and reproduction, high seed dispersal ability, a physiological adaptability to new conditions and a knack to survive on a wide range of food types and environmental (including hydrological) conditions.

The more commonly used term, weed, a subset of IAS, is simply used for any plant which is considered undesirable in a particular setting. *Allelopathy* is the biological phenomenon exhibited by weeds (and other invasive species) by which they release biochemicals (called allelochemicals or allelochemicals) through various processes into the environment, which are usually detrimental to the other plant species in their vicinity (An et al. 1998). Allelochemicals, which may be present in virtually all plant tissues, including leaves, flowers, roots, stems, seeds and pollen, generally consist of compounds like alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolics, glucosinolates and terpenoids. These in turn, may lead to inhibited

germination rate, lower reproductive capacity, swollen seeds, damage to roots (through curling of root axis, loss of root hairs) and reduced dry weight accumulation in the surrounding plants.

All the above factors affect either directly or indirectly the ability of a native plant to extract water from the hydrological basin for the consumptive water use. Changes in land cover due to a combination of the relative suppression in the growth of the native plants and the relative build-up of alien species may also affect the water balance of the soil-vegetation-atmosphere system. The allelopathic release of biochemicals harmful to other plants may also lead to significantly unsafe environment for humans. The possible change in groundwater chemistry may affect potable groundwater availability. The allelochemicals may also affect animals and/or animal products and may be dangerous to both cattle and human consumers.

1.2 Effect of Alien Species on water balance

A study looking into the effect of an invasion of the fynbos shrublands (natural shrubland vegetation of a part of the Western Cape of South Africa) by woody weeds, in the context of catchment hydrology (Maitre et al. 1996) reveals dramatic reductions in the water yield of the invaded catchment. The catchment, majorly consisting of vegetation types including mesic (with a moderate to well-balanced supply of moisture) and dry mountain fynbos shrublands, was invaded by IAS such as *Pinus pinaster*, *A. longifolia*, *A. saligna* and *Leptospermum laevigatum*. A GIS based model which established a relationship between the measured streamflow reduction (mm) and the amount of vegetation-related biomass (g/m^2) estimated an annual mean water yield reduction of $350 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}$, which was equivalent to a 10.6% reduction in an invaded catchment as compared to an uninvaded one.

Maitre et al. (2002) carried out a preliminary cost assessment of control operations started at the current levels of invasion by plantation species, compared to those which would start after allowing the catchments to be fully invaded. The 4 river catchments in South Africa, which were the focus of their study, had been chosen by the government for plantation of alien trees (pines and eucalypts) because of their purported benefits to the GDP (2%) and employment (over 100,000 people). Unfortunately, many of the plantation species became invaders, and model estimates showed a surface runoff reduction of about 6-22% (across catchments) of the total runoff, which is significant when it was noted that water is a primary yet scarce resource for development. The runoff reduction was projected to increase to about 22-95%, should the catchments be allowed complete invasion. The cost to prevent such losses would increase from about US\$ 4-13 million to about about US\$ 11-278 million, in the same circumstances.

1.3 Motivation and Objectives of the Study

Parthenium hysterophorus is a highly invasive alien weed, and its continuously growing presence in the fertile crop-producing plains of North India is a cause for concern not only from the point of view of its health and inhibitory effects on crop growth, but also in terms of a possible significant effect on the water balance of a river basin. Although its dermatological and allelopathic properties have been researched upon, a basic study incorporating its possible hydrological effects is urgently needed. Water is widely acknowledged as a key factor for agricultural productivity, and a key constraint to economic growth, and thus there exists a reasonable pressure for the sustainable and efficient use of this limited resource. To know if the presence of *Parthenium* affects its

availability is essential for the management of water to determine the cost of controlling the spread of *Parthenium*.

The primary objectives of this study are:

- i. To explore the literature for understanding the physical, allelopathic, biochemical and physiological properties of *Parthenium hysterophorus* and its impacts on the water balance of a river basin.
- ii. To identify parameters which are vital for estimating the hydrological effects of *Parthenium* and determining their values from the literature and/or by conducting controlled experiments.
- iii. To test the effect of a *Parthenium* invasion on the water balance of a river basin using a hydrological model.

1.4 Organisation of the Thesis

This thesis is organized in seven chapters. The present chapter gives a brief description of IAS and the motivation behind this work. Chapter 2 presents various aspects of *Parthenium hysterophorus* from the literature. Chapter 3 describes the motivation, setup, analysis and results of the transpiration experiments that were conducted. Chapter 4 describes the purpose, formulation and results of the mathematical formulation of the Penman Monteith evapotranspiration method used for ET studies. Chapter 5 includes the motivation, description of study area, SWAT model setup, data used for simulation and results of the hydrological modeling conducted. Chapter 6 summarises the work done and the results obtained. Chapter 7 outlines the scope of possible future work that could be done in this direction.

Chapter 2

Parthenium hysterophorus

2.1 Introduction

Parthenium hysterophorus is a flowering and a common invasive alien species in India. It is a species native to north-east Mexico, North and South Americas and gained recognition as a threat when it allegedly entered India as a contaminant in PL 480 wheat imported from the USA in the 1950s, thus being coined as *Congress grass* (Kumari 2014). It is also locally called *gajar ghans/ gaajari* (because of the resemblance of its leaves to the leaves of the carrot plant), *chatak chandani*, ‘Scourge of India’, and in other parts of the world as feverfew, white top (or *safed topi* in Hindi), star weed and bitter weed. It has been listed in the Global Invasive Species Database and is widespread in India – about 2 million hectares of land in India (mainly in Punjab, Haryana and Uttar Pradesh) were reported to have been infested by *Parthenium* (Dwivedi et al. 2009). Apart from causing contact dermatitis, allergic respiratory problems, mutagenicity in humans and livestock, crop production is also affected due to its allelopathic properties. Its aggressively invasive behavior also threatens the native biodiversity of the region of its spread.

2.2 Botanical description

The botanical taxonomy of the *Parthenium hysterophorus* is- Division: *Magnoliophyta*; Class: *Magnoliopsida*, Order: *Asterales*; Family: *Asteraceae*; Genus: *Parthenium*; Species: *hysterophorus*.

Growing up to a maximum height of 2m, its main stem is green while it is growing and branching becomes highly prevalent at the time of flowering for a higher seed production.

Figure 2.5(a): Basal rosette formed by the leaves of *Parthenium*

Figure 2.1(b): The terminal white flowers of *Parthenium*

Its leaves are deeply lobed, bipinnate, pale green, upto 30 cm in length, and like the stem, are covered with fine hairs called trichomes. There are about 6-55 leaves per plant; leaves initially form a basal rosette (Figure 2.1(a)), and most of them die after flowering, and only the ribs of the stem remain. Flowers heads (about 4 mm across) are creamy-white, and occur at the terminals of the stem and its branches (Figure 2.1(b)). Each flower contains five wedge shaped, 2 mm long seeds, with thin white scales. A single plant can potentially produce up to 100,000 seeds in one life cycle, which can spread with a surface density of more than 340 million seeds per hectare (Sankaran 2008). It has one main taproot branching into finer roots.

2.3 Spread and Growth

Seed dispersal is generally through animals, water currents, and movement of vehicles, livestock, grain, stock feed, and machinery. Long distance spreading occurs through

flooding, farm machinery and vehicles. Germination of seeds can occur between 8° and 30°C but the optimum germination temperature is around 22° to 25°C (Sankaran 2008). Flowering occurs in about a month after the onset of germination, and a life cycle is completed in within 3-4 months. Its ability to complete three to four generations in one year only adds to a potentially larger spread and more adverse impacts (Kumari 2014). It can

Figure 2.6: Patch of *Parthenium* growth next to roadside (IIT Kanpur campus, July 2013)

grow on almost all soil types, but prefers alkaline, clay loam to heavy black clay soils. Its growth is reduced in water logged or exceptionally dry soil. It can get established in land uses as diverse as roadsides (Figure 2.2), wasteland, railway tracks, forests and crop fields. Interestingly, it spreads most rapidly in semi-dry soil, common during summer, and because of lesser competitors (due to the heat and water stressed conditions). It remains as a rosette during summer and grows briskly at the onset of the monsoons.

Due to its high capacity for regeneration, it can grow from root stumps, petioles, or even midribs left in the soil (Gupta et al. 1977).

2.4 Chemical Analysis

Phytochemicals such as alkaloids, sesquiterpene lactones (parthenin and coronopilin), p-coumaric acid, kaempferol, and phenolic acids are present in almost all plant parts of *P. hysterophorus* such as trichomes, leaves, pollens and inflorescence (Kumari 2014). Other phytotoxic compounds like ambrosin, hysterin, flavonoids such as quercelagetin 3,7 – dimethylether, 6-hydroxyl kaempferol 3-0 arabinoglucoside, fumaric acid, vanillic acid and P-hydroxy benzoin, p-courmaric, anisic acid, p-anisic acid, caffeic acid, chlorogenic acid, sitosterol, ferulic acid and some other unidentified alcohols were found in *P. hysterophorus* (Figure 2.3). Parthenin, hymenin and ambrosin (major sesquiterpene lactones and phenolic acids) are the allelochemicals which are responsible for its major allelopathic effects (Patel 2011).

Figure 2.7: Allelochemicals found in *Parthenium hysterophorus* (Patel 2011)

The autotoxicity (allelopathy in which an allelopathic species inhibits its own growth or reproduction) of these water soluble sesquiterpene lactones and phenolic acids had also been examined by (Picman and Picman 1984) who reported that these allelochemicals are autotoxic to older plants and seedlings even at a 0.1% concentration. These allelochemicals play a vital role not only to defend the plant against diseases and predators (herbivores), but also in the regulation of population and the timings of the germination process.

2.5 Impacts of *Parthenium hysterophorus*

2.5.1 Impacts on Human Health

The pollen and dust from *P. hysterophorus* causes allergic contact dermatitis in humans.

Figure 2.8(a): *Parthenium* contact dermatitis causing blister-like formations on hands (Sharma et al. 2013)

Figure 2.4(b): *Parthenium* airborne contact dermatitis (Sharma et al. 2013)

People exposed for prolonged periods to *Parthenium* may begin showing symptoms of skin inflammation, asthma, eczema (Figure 2.4(a)), allergic rhinitis, black spots, hay fever (sinusitis), burning and blisters around eyes (Figure 2.4(b)). The sesquiterpene lactone

parthenin is majorly responsible for cytotoxicity (the property of being toxic to cells) and is related to such symptoms (Patel 2011).

2.5.2 Impact on Livestock

Loss of hair (alopecia) and skin pigmentation, diarrhoea and dermatitis has been observed in animals feeding on *Parthenium*. Deteriorative changes in the kidneys and liver of buffalo and sheep have also been reported (Patel 2011). A significant amount (10-50%) of *Parthenium* in the diet may even cause death in cattle. The meat and milk quality of cattle,

Figure 2.5: Proximity of grazing cattle to *Parthenium* growth (IIT Kanpur campus, July 2013)

sheep and buffalo also degrade on the consumption of this weed.

2.5.3 Impact on Crop Productivity

Parthenium hysterophorus may cause a decline in crop yield up to 40% in India (Khosla and Sobti 1981). Parthenin leaching through exudation from the roots is vital to the allelopathic role of the weed towards its surrounding crops and pastures. When the remains

of its fallen leaves enter the surrounding soil and subsequently decompose, it has been reported as a germination and radicle growth inhibitor (Patel 2011). *Parthenium* pollen can inhibit fruit set in eggplant, tomatoes, beans and pepper. Due to its extremely high dispersal and difficulty in stopping its spread, crop plant seeds are contaminated with *Parthenium* seeds and this naturally restricts their sales (Kumari 2014).

2.5.4 Biodiversity Loss

Changes in the land cover are natural consequences of invasive species, but *Parthenium*'s highly allelopathic invasive capacity has resulted in very sparse or no vegetation in areas of its dominance. It has caused habitat changes in Australian grasslands, open woodlands, flood plains and river banks by reducing the number and growth of native plants (Patel 2011).

2.6 Control of *P. hysterophorus*

2.6.1 Cultural Control

This includes several good practices such as keeping equipment clean, bathing livestock, washing animal feed, and preventing physical spread of seeds by machinery, tires, cultivators or footwear. Burning entire stands of *Parthenium* may kill the plant parts which are above the ground but the dispersed seeds which were already buried may survive (Kumari 2014). Also, burning the above ground weed is not recommended as it renders soil more alkaline and deficient in organic matter, thus leading to a decline in soil quality. Growth of *P. hysterophorus* can also be suppressed by growing competitive crops (maize,

fodder sorghum sunflower) or self-perpetuating species like *C. tora*, *Abutilon indicum*, *Tagetes erecta* (marigold) *Cassia auriculata* and *Cassia sericea*.

2.6.2 Chemical Control

Synthetic herbicides like paraquat, simazine, 2,4-D,2,4,5-T glyphosate, alachlor, Atrazine and Metribuzin have been tried and found effective in controlling *P. hysterophorus* invasions, but the timing of application is crucial. These methods are effective if the plants are treated before flowering and seed setting, ensuring that the surrounding plants are actively growing simultaneously and can recolonise the invaded region. Infestations in open wastelands and non-cropped areas (adjacent to roadsides and railway tracks) can be tackled by spraying a solution of 15-20% concentration of common salt (sodium chloride). However, excessive use of herbicides, apart from threatening the environment, may not affect the root stumps, stolons or suckers, which are under the ground, and buried seeds may also germinate. An excessive dependence on herbicides may also manifest into more resistant weeds.

2.6.3 Biological Control

Figure 2.6(a): Young *Zygrogramma bicolorata* on the stem of a *Parthenium* plant

Figure 2.6(b) The stem-galling moth *Epiblema strenuana* (CSIRO Ecosystem Sciences)

Several pathogens and insects have been tried to control the spread of *P. hysterophorus*. The leaf-feeding beetle *Zygrogramma bicolorata* (Figure 2.6(a)) and the stem-galling moth *Epiblema strenuana* (Figure 2.6(b)) have been used in the management of *Parthenium*. The moth reduces flower and seed production and both of the insects' effectiveness has been validated in Australia (Dhileepan 2003). The leaf rust *Puccinia melampodi* and moth *Carmenta ithacae* were released unsuccessfully since the weed has a very high regenerative potential, and additionally, the insect consumes only the foliage of the weed; the flowers and seeds remain untouched (Dhileepan and Strathie 2009). Other pathogens like *Fusarium pallidroseum*, and *Oidium parthenii* may also be potential biocontrol agents (Kumari 2014).

2.7 Hydrological study of *Parthenium*: Literature Review

A study which measured various growth, reproductive and photosynthesis-related parameters of *Parthenium hysterophorus* weed was undertaken by (Pandey et al. 2003) in Almora (Uttaranchal, India) in 1996 and 1997, for two stands, representing summer (May-July) and winter (October-December) conditions. The experimental setup had controls for temperature, relative humidity and (RH), photosynthetic photon flux (which is a measure of the area-energy density per unit time, of the radiation which is actively used by plants for photosynthesis, having wavelength in the range of 400-700 nm) and CO₂ concentration. Some of the parameters which were reported and which were relevant to a hydrologic study were the Leaf Area Index, (leaf level) stomatal conductance, mean plant height and transpiration.

2.7.1 Methodology of study

Parthenium seeds were sown in 3 plots at the beginning of April and October for two consecutive years, 1996 and 1997. 10 plants which were assumed to be representative of the population were sampled from each sample plot 50 days after emergence, just before flowering occurred. Plant height and leaf area (using a portable leaf area meter) were measured immediately after sampling. A gas exchange monitoring system was set up using an open-flow gas-exchange system, which had a built in light source and carbon dioxide injection system. A calibrated CO₂-H₂O analyser calibrated using known values of CO₂ concentration from a cylinder and known values of water vapour concentration using a humidity dew point was used. Humidified air, after being bubbled through water was controlled for RH values using a desiccant. Stomatal conductance and transpiration measurements were measured using this setup.

2.7.2 Leaf Area Index

The leaf area index (LAI), which is defined as the one-sided leaf area (in m^2) per unit ground area (in m^2), is a key parameter for scaling up stomatal gas and water vapour exchange from leaf to canopy level (Brèda 2003). It is generally difficult to quantify correctly, owing to its temporal and spatial variability. There are 5 common definitions of LAI, depending on the required purpose, reported by Barclay (1998).

- The Total Leaf Area Index (TLAI) is based on the total outside area of leaves, and is rarely reported in the literature.
- The One-sided Leaf Area Index (OLAI) is more common in the literature. As its name suggests, it is a measure of one side of the green leaf area per unit ground area, even if the 2 sides of the leaf are not symmetrical.
- The horizontally Projected Leaf Area (PLAI) is the projected area of the leaf per unit ground area, measured perpendicular to the light source assumed at an infinite distance. This is being used more commonly in the recent literature.
- The inclined projected leaf area/ Silhouette Leaf Area Index (SLAI) uses the projected leaf area while taking into account leaf inclination with the direction of the light propagation.
- The fifth definition is a modification of the SLAI which incorporates the overlap of leaves in a developed canopy of the vegetation in question.

The portable leaf area meter Li-Cor LAI-2000 which was used for leaf area measurements uses the SLAI definition to compute leaf area, and hence a factor of half which is used in

the cases where the 'effective' leaf area is to be employed in computations, is not necessary for measurements using this instrument.

There are different techniques of measurement of leaf area which can be broadly divided into Direct and Indirect Methods. Direct methods are contact based, are time consuming, labour intensive and unrealistic for large scale measurements, but their importance as calibration for validation of Indirect methods is worth noting. Direct methods which use destructive sampling work on the assumption that there exists a lateral homogeneity of the stand of the plant being studied. Harvest methods, litter trap method and allometric methods are commonly used Direct methods for LAI measurement. Indirect Methods may be either contact or non-contact, but are generally more feasible for larger scales. The Inclined point quadrat method and allometric techniques are examples of Indirect contact methods. Indirect non-contact methods work on physical principles (like the Beer Lambert Law) which govern the transmission of light through a canopy. The concept being used by measuring differential light above and below the canopy, or by measuring the canopy distribution itself. Gap fraction analysis, Gap size distribution analysis are two popular indirect methods (Jonckheere et al. 2004).

The LAI plays an important role in determining and controlling canopy water interception, radiation extinction, water and carbon dioxide gas exchange. us in estimating the ability of a plant to carry out photosynthesis as well as respiration (which is also linked to transpiration losses). Table 4.2 shows the reported values for leaf area index for the period of study.

2.7.3 Mean plant height

Mean plant height (m) was measured to the apical meristem, and reported values, for stands of both seasons during both the years are given in Table 4.2.

2.7.4 Stomatal conductance

Stomatal conductance ($\text{mmol/m}^2/\text{s}$) is defined as a rate measure of the passage of CO_2 entering, or water vapour exiting through leaf stomata. Stomata are the pores found on the epidermal layer of majorly leaves, but also the stem and some other plant organs. Section 2.7 explains the role of stomatal conductance in plant physiology. The values chosen for mathematical modeling are listed in Table 4.2.

2.7.5 Plant transpiration

Experiments were attempted to find out the marginal effects of light, temperature and RH on the transpiration by *Parthenium*.

- **Effect of temperature on transpiration:** Keeping the RH constant at 30% and maintaining ambient CO_2 levels, transpiration patterns were observed with changing PPF (photosynthetic photon flux in $\mu\text{mol/m}^2/\text{s}$) for four different temperatures which were assumed to cover a range of temperatures in which *Parthenium* grows (7°C , 25°C , 35°C , 47°C). The lowest temperature, 7°C is representative of the frost spells which occur during winter, especially in December. And the highest temperature, 47°C is closer to the peak temperatures reached during the afternoon, in the hottest part of summer. The observations are reported in Figure 2.7.

Figure 2.7: Effect of temperature and photosynthetic photon flux on transpiration at ambient CO₂ levels and 30% RH (Pandey et al. 2003)

Transpiration was not very significantly affected by the change of PPF at a constant temperature, but irrespective of PPF, transpiration doubled from 7° to 25°C, and from 25° to 35°C, and actually tripled when temperatures were raised from 35° to 47 °C. This means that temperature, rather than light intensity, is a major factor affecting the rate of transpiration.

- **Effect of RH on transpiration:** Keeping ambient CO₂ concentrations and 25°C temperature, the RH levels were changed from 30% to 60% and changes in transpiration were observed, which are given in Figure 2.8.

Figure 2.8: Effect of Relative Humidity and PPF on transpiration at ambient CO_2 levels and 25°C temperature (Pandey et al. 2003)

It was seen that the level of RH in the atmosphere was not a determinant of the rate of transpiration, and perhaps in support of the concept that the vapour pressure deficit (the difference between concentrations of ambient water vapour and water vapour inside the leaf) was a more significant driving force of transpiration.

2.8 Plant Physiology: Transpiration and *Parthenium* as a C3-C4 intermediate species

2.8.1 Plant physiological aspect of transpiration

There is an inherent conflict for any plant between the need to assimilate CO_2 during photosynthesis, and the need to conserve water. This arises as the major inlets and outlets of these exchanges are the stomatal openings present on the surface of the leaves. Water is pulled from the xylem (the tissue which transports water and nutrients upwards through the plant) into the mesophyll (a tissue that lies between the upper and lower epidermis layers of the leaf) and evaporates into air spaces within the leaf. Water vapour subsequently diffuses through the stomatal pores, and across the boundary layer of the still air adjacent to the leaf

surface (Figure 2.9). The major factor which drives transpiration is the difference in the water vapour concentration between the external air and the leaf air spaces, limited by the diffusional resistance of this pathway, which is analogous to a series of electrical resistances formed by the stomatal resistance (r_s) and the resistance offered by the layer of still air next to the leaf (r_b). The transpiration rate (in $\text{mol/m}^2/\text{s}$), according to Taiz and Zeiger (2010) can be given by:

$$E = \frac{c_{wv(leaf)} - c_{wv(air)}}{r_s + r_b} \quad (2.1)$$

where

E = transpiration rate [$\text{mol/m}^2/\text{s}$]

$c_{wv(leaf)}$ = concentration of water vapour inside the air spaces within the leaf
[mol/m^3]

$c_{wv(air)}$ = concentration of water vapour in the air outside the leaf [mol/m^3]

r_s = resistance at the stomatal pore [s/m]

r_b = resistance of the boundary layer adjacent to the leaf [s/m]

The water vapour concentrations can be expressed in pressure terms (in units of kPa) and then the collective term $c_{wv(leaf)} - c_{wv(air)}$ is called the vapour pressure deficit. Apart from when the wind speed is very low, it is safe to assume that most of the resistance offered by the leaf is contributed by the stomatal resistance, which is regulated principally by the guard cells (a pair of epidermal cells surrounding each stomatal pore), which modify the stomatal aperture (size of opening) to meet the photosynthetic CO_2 demand while minimizing water loss (Figure 2.9).

Figure 2.9: Pathway of water through the leaf. Water movement is in the opposite direction to its concentration gradient. (Taiz and Zeiger, 2010)

It is possible to measure readily the water vapour concentration of air, but water vapour concentration inside the leaf is much more difficult to assess. With the assumption that the air space inside the leaf is in water potential equilibrium with the cell walls, we can estimate $c_{wv(leaf)}$ if we know the water potential of the leaf (which is the same as the water potential for the cell wall) and the leaf temperature, using the formula given below:

$$\psi_w = \frac{RT}{\bar{V}_w} \ln(RH) \quad (2.2)$$

where

ψ_w = water potential (a measure of free energy per unit volume) [J/m^3]

R = gas constant (=8.314 J/mol/K)

T = temperature [K]

RH = relative humidity of the water vapour [dimensionless]

V_w = partial molar volume of liquid water

If we know the leaf water potential and the leaf temperature, then using equation (2.2) we can estimate out the relative humidity of the air inside the leaf and subsequently find the water vapour concentration using Equation (2.3)

$$RH = \frac{c_{wv}}{c_{wv(sat)}} \quad (2.3)$$

where

$c_{wv(sat)}$ = saturation water vapour concentration [mol/m³]

Saturation vapour pressure concentration strongly depends on temperature, and therefore the water vapour concentration inside the leaf can be computed.

2.8.2 *Parthenium* as a C3-C4 intermediate

C3, C4 and CAM are mechanisms of carbon fixation used by plants in the photosynthetic process, the major difference being in their ability to avoid water vapour loss through transpiration. The numbers '3' and '4' represent the number of C-atoms present in the first stable product of carbon fixation. While the C3 plants are found most commonly, many plants which survive in more light intensive, hotter and drier conditions (also known as xerophytic conditions) use the C4 mechanism, which is a more efficient method for net photosynthesis (Taiz and Zeiger 2010).

C3 plants have mesophyll cells and bundle sheath cells, both present in the homogenous chloroplasts, which work simultaneously during the day to the effect of absorbing atmospheric CO₂ through the stomata during the day for the photosynthetic process, at the cost of inevitable water vapour loss to the atmosphere.

C4 plants are generally found in areas of water stress and high light intensity, have a physiological modification called the Kranz Anatomy, in which a separation is observed in the chloroplast between the mesophyll cells and bundle sheath cells. The direct consequence of this modification is that the mesophyll cells can absorb atmospheric CO₂ during the night, and this CO₂ then goes through a series of conversions during the night, after which it is finally reconverted in the separated bundle sheath cells to metabolic CO₂ during the day and used in the carbohydrate producing processes (Calvin cycle). But the aspect which is of more interest, from a hydrologic point of view, is that since C4 plants open their stomata only at night, their water vapour loss through transpiration is considerably reduced (Taiz and Zeiger 2010).

Parthenium is a C3-C4 intermediate, and its leaves have C3 mesophyll cells and non-Kranz leaf anatomy on the adaxial (upper) leaf surface and C4 mesophyll with Kranz leaf anatomy on the abaxial (lower) surface of the leaf (Rajendrudu and Das 1990). This may be a reason of its ability to thrive, and even spread in the peak summer as well (using its relatively more efficient usage of water), when there is a reduced chance of the survival of other competing plants in the vicinity.

Chapter 3

Phytometer Experiments

3.1 Introduction

One of the key assumptions in the estimation of evapotranspiration (or for that matter any water balance related parameter) from numerical models is that the model, along with all the input parameters, is a representation of the physical reality it is attempting to emulate. Hence the governing physical laws, when applied, would give predictions which are expected to be an accurate description of the variables in the real world. A phytometer (*phyto-* plant) experiment investigates growth of relevant species, under controlled conditions, in different soils, to test the effect of defined variables on the growth of plants (Wheeler et al. 1992). The phytometer experiments in this study are a modification of the standard phytometer experiment. The modifications were done to account for inadequate control over the climate and soil-related inputs in our laboratory and also because the observed variables were not primarily related to plant growth, but were related to water losses.

3.2 Purpose of the experiment

The primary purpose of the experiment was to facilitate a comparison between the estimated evapotranspiration (ET) from the Penman Monteith method with observations. The experiments were designed to compare the ET losses from *Parthenium*, a sample of the locally available reference grass (which in this case was Bermuda grass or *doob*), and a sample representing the evaporation from non-vegetated soil.

3.3 Experimental setup, Assumptions and Limitations

3.3.1 Experimental Setup

The experiment was carried out in two phases – one which spanned September 3rd, 2013 to December 15th, 2013 and the second one spanning May 13th, 2014 to May 17th, 2014. The conceptualization of both the experiments was the same: samples of *Parthenium* and common grasses were planted in pots, and watered every morning, and the difference in measured weights between the start and the end of a day would give a measure for the losses from the sample plant, on any given day. The experimental setup is described below:

10 concrete pots were used to plant samples – 5 *Parthenium* plants, 4 grasses and 1 pot serving as a representative of non-vegetated soil. The pots were measured for weight, so that the weights of the pots could be normalized later. There were 2 reference grasses (and 2 specimens of each) in the first experiment and the second experiment used only one grass (Bermuda grass or *doob*). The plant samples were collected along with the soil, from natural *Parthenium* outgrowths within the IIT Kanpur campus. The soils were mostly a combination of loam, sand and clay, the typical soils found in the region. The plants were allowed to grow in their new environment for around a week, and it was ensured that they faced no water stress, by regular watering. During the experiment, the pots were kept in the open, so that they faced true climatic variables. Each pot was covered with a plastic sheet, so that the losses apart from soil evaporation and plant transpiration, for instance the water that leaked out from the hole at the base of a pot, could be contained within the total weight of the plant, trying to ensure maximum accuracy in measurements. During the first experiment that was conducted in the monsoon season, the pots were brought indoors while

it rained, to avoid water logging. There was no such requirement during the second experiment, which was carried out during the summer.

Figure 3.1: Experimental setup of phytometer experiment – 4 pots with *Parthenium*, 3 pots with Bermuda grass (*doob*) and one representative of non-vegetated soil

3.3.2 Modifications to improve the limitations of the first experiment:

- The experiments consisted watering the plants once in the morning every day, noting the weight, and repeating similar measurements during the day. For Experiment 1, measurements were taken twice a day, once at 8AM and another time at 5PM. It was realized that to properly understand the dynamic process of transpiration throughout the day, and to look at intra-day patterns of water losses, it was important to take more readings in a day. For Experiment 2, measurements were taken at hourly intervals, from 8AM to 5PM.
- 400g of water was added every day in Experiment 1, to each pot, and it was observed that the water was invariably used up during the day, and may have possible led to water stressed conditions in some pots. It was important that each

plant had the ability to carry out stomatal transpiration without any restrictions imposed by the environmental conditions (soil moisture in this case). Thus the amount of water added was increased to 800-900g in Experiment 2.

- A weighing machine with a least count of 50g was chosen for Experiment 1, and it was later realized that daily transpiration from plants required much finer scales of measurement if meaningful inferences were to be made. Thus, for Experiment 2, a weighing machine with a least count of 1g was used.
- In Experiment 1, water losses were reported in the units of weight (g), which was assumed to be the obvious choice of reporting. But as transpiration is not a function of the weight of the soil-pot-plant system, but more of the potential capacity of stomatal openings to allow the gaseous exchange, it was decided to report transpiration values per unit leaf area. Leaf area was approximated by using representative leaves of each specimen, pasting them on standard graph papers, and manually measuring the area as a function of the number of squares which were concealed by the leaf (Figure3.2). Multiple measurements were then averaged for a single leaf area value.

Figure 3.2: Leaf Area measurement for a specimen *Parthenium* leaf: each small square has an area of 1 mm^2

3.3.3 Assumptions and their associated Limitations

- It was assumed that there was no water stress that the plants faced during any substantial period during the day. This was attempted to be ensured by enough watering at the beginning of the day. Since there were no soil-moisture measurements that were carried out, it cannot be said with certainty that water stress conditions were avoided at all times.
- It was assumed that other losses (apart from ET) were the same in all the pots, so that ET values could be compared. Since the plastic bags which were used to seal the pots and prevent leakage did not always perform as expected, it is possible that there were losses which were unaccounted for.
- It was assumed that the soil properties were more or less constant across pots. Since the experiments focused on comparing the differences between *Parthenium* and other grasses (i.e. a comparison between different species of plants), the assumption was reasonable.

- The leaf area (for Experiment 2) was measured at the end of the experiment, and reported as a constant. Whereas actually the leaf area is dynamic and changes with plant growth. But the assumption is justifiable because Experiment 2 was carried out over a period of a week, and plant growth was not very substantial when compared to the actual length of a season of the plant.

3.4 Results

3.4.1 General physiological observations

In a phytometer experiment focusing on hydrological aspects of plants such as water balance, the context of any hydrological system being an open system and the dynamics of plant responses to environmental factors that in turn regulate transpiration, should not be overlooked.

- During Experiment 2 (in May 2014), one of the *Parthenium* plants could not survive the extreme heat and sunlight conditions, even though it was well watered every day. This can be attributed to either the soil being very unsuitable for its growth, or a human error while transporting the specimen from the field to the pot, adversely affecting its health, and chances of survival.
- In another *Parthenium* plant which also seemed to be unhealthy by the end of the experimental period, new flowers were observed at the shoot terminal (Figure 3.3), which were not present earlier during the experiment. This may be due to a mechanism to increase the chances of germination by increasing seed dispersal.

- One *Parthenium* specimen whose health deteriorated to near death conditions, but actually survived the experimental period, grew a new, smaller offshoot from the tip of its dying stem (Figure 3.4) suggesting the adaptability of the plant for its survival.

Figure 3.3: Wilting *Parthenium* plant growing flowers from shoot terminal

Figure 3.4: *Parthenium* plant in bad health growing new offshoot from stem tip

3.4.2 Transpiration Results

Physical measurements and computations related to each pot used in the study are given in Table 3.1.

Table 3.2: Observable properties of plant sample pots used in the study (* - Soil surface area)

Plant sample	Diameter of soil surface (cm)	Number of green leaves	Averaged leaf area per leaf (cm ²)	Total leaf area (m ²)	Leaf area Index (LAI) (m ² /m ²)
<i>Parthenium</i> (P1)	18.5	15	5.27	79.05	0.292
<i>Parthenium</i> (P2)	17.5	39	5.27	205.53	0.854
<i>Parthenium</i> (P3)	18.5	81	5.27	426.87	1.588
Bermuda grass (G1)	18	170	0.79	134.3	0.528
Bermuda grass (G2)	18.5	216	0.79	170.64	0.635
Bermuda grass (G3)	18.5	52	0.79	41.08	0.153
Soil sample	18	NA	NA	254.46*	

The plot for the hourly water losses from each pot, for 3 days, is given in Figure 3.5. Measurements are reported as water lost (gm) per unit total leaf area (cm^2) per unit water added at the beginning of the day (gm).

Figure 3.5: Measurements of water loss per unit leaf area per unit water added ($\text{gm}/\text{m}^2/\text{gm}$) of 3 *Parthenium* (P) and 3 Bermuda grass (*doob*) (G) samples.

On an average, the rate of water loss increased as the day progressed, and then reduced as the evenings set in. This can be attributed to the ambient temperature and light intensity, both increasing to a maximum in the afternoon, and decreasing back to relatively lower values in the evening. Another observation is that in *Parthenium* the rate of water loss is less than or around Bermuda grass. One Bermuda specimen lost water consistently at a higher rate than any Bermuda grass sample perhaps because of water losses even other than ET despite the attempts at sealing the pot. Even after excluding this particular sample, the ET losses from *Parthenium* on an average are still marginally lower than the ET losses from the Bermuda grass. The ASCE Penman Monteith method (Walter et al. 2005) for estimating evapotranspiration assumes that among plant parameters, plant height, leaf area

index and stomatal conductance are responsible for regulating transpiration. The maximum stomatal conductance for *Parthenium* was reported as 0.00584 m/s (Pandey et al. 2003) and that for Bermuda grass was reported to be 0.005 m/s (Arc SWAT land use-plant database). The mean leaf area for *Parthenium* (237.15 cm²) is higher than Bermuda grass (115.34 cm²) thus it indicates that *Parthenium* has higher opportunity for stomatal exchange of gases, with the assumption that plant health is optimum for all plants. Further, the *Parthenium* plants were not higher than the Bermuda grass plants to the extent that it would reduce aerodynamic resistance and ease the ET process. Additionally, taking into account the marginal difference in stomatal conductance, it is possible that the ET values of *Parthenium* were lowered further due to their poorer health as compared to Bermuda grass, due to a decrease in the photosynthetic ability of the plants.

Chapter 4

Mathematical Modeling of Evapotranspiration

4.1 Evapotranspiration

Evapotranspiration (ET) represents the process of exchange of mass and energy within the soil-water-vegetation system and the atmosphere. It is a combination of two processes – evaporation and transpiration. Evaporation is the transfer of mass and energy from open surfaces like water bodies, bare ground and intercepted water collected on the surface of vegetation. Transpiration involves the absorption of available water from the soil by vegetation and its transport through the plant and release into the atmosphere mainly through the leaves and sometimes through the cuticular tissue, after having been used by the plant for growth related processes (Senay et al. 2011). ET is a major component of the water balance of a catchment, and the knowledge of the amount and rate of ET is critical in the prediction of water yields, the design of irrigation and supply projects, the management of water quality and quantity, and associated environmental concerns, and in the negotiation of conflicts, contracts or treaties involving water (Hasenmueller and Criss 2013). ET estimation is also essential to quantify the role of a plant species in the water balance of a catchment.

4.2 Motivation for estimating ET

To study the effect of changing land cover representing the spread of *Parthenium*, it was necessary to quantify the effect of *Parthenium* on the water balance components. The Penman-Monteith equation (Monteith 1965) was selected for ET estimates. The Penman

Method is a physical model which integrates weather parameters and plant parameters to estimate ET, and the ASCE Standardised Penman Monteith equation (2005) is recommended to be used for ET calculations (Sammis et al. 2011). To get a perspective on how *Parthenium* changes the ‘ET-scape’ of the area it invades, two direct comparisons were made for summer and winter using the ET values of a *kharif* crop (Maize) and a *rabi* crop (Durum Wheat), respectively, as reference crops. Maize and durum wheat were selected because these are vital agricultural crops which grow during their respective seasons and any differences in their ET losses with respect to *Parthenium* would be critical to understand the effects of *Parthenium* invasion on water balance.

4.3 The Penman-Monteith Method

The Penman-Monteith (PM) equation estimates actual evapotranspiration (ET) given the input of average temperature (over the time scale), wind speed, solar radiation and relative humidity. The American Society of Civil Engineers (ASCE) Penman-Monteith Method uses the following combination equation for the reference evapotranspiration:

$$ET_{ref} = \frac{\Delta(R_n - G) + K_{time}\rho_a C_p(e_s - e_a)/r_a}{\lambda\rho_w[\Delta + \gamma(1 + \frac{r_s}{r_a})]} \quad (4.1)$$

where

ET_{ref} = reference evapotranspiration [mm/d or mm/hr]

Δ = slope of the saturation vapor pressure-temperature relationship [KPa/°C]

R_n = net radiation [MJ/m²/day or MJ/m²/hr]

G = soil heat flux [MJ/m²/day or MJ/m²/hr]

$e_s - e_a$ = vapor pressure deficit of air [kPa]

e_s = saturation vapor pressure of the air [kPa]

e_a = actual vapor pressure of the air [kPa]

K_{time} = units conversion [86400 s/d when ET_o is in mm/d and 3600 s/hr when ET_o in mm/hr]

ρ_a = mean air density at constant pressure [kg/m^3]

C_p = specific heat of the air [$\text{MJ}/\text{kg}/^\circ\text{C}$]

r_a = aerodynamic resistance [s/m]

r_s = (bulk) surface resistance [s/m]

λ = latent heat of vaporization [MJ/kg]

γ = psychrometric constant [$\text{kPa}/^\circ\text{C}$]

ρ_w = density of water [Mg/m^3] taken as $1.0 \text{ Mg}/\text{m}^3$

Here, the aerodynamic resistance is a function of the heights at which measurements are taken, wind speed and the mean height of the vegetation. Bulk surface resistance is a function of the leaf area index (LAI) and effective stomatal resistance of an illuminated leaf.

The Standardized Reference Evapotranspiration equation (Walter et al. 2005) uses 2 reference crops with appropriate constants and standardised computational procedures:

ET_{os} is the reference ET for a short crop with an approximated height of 0.12m and $r_s = 70$ s/m (daily time step) or 50 s/m (hourly time step during daytime), similar to clipped, cool season grass.

ET_{rs} is the reference ET for a tall crop with an approximated height of 0.5m and $r_s = 45$ s/m (daily time step) or 30 s/m (hourly time step during daytime) and is similar to full cover alfalfa. Both the grasses have $r_s = 200$ s/m during nighttime (calculated for hourly time step).

Incorporating these constants into Equation (1) gives us the following Standardised Reference ET equation:

$$ET_{sz} = \frac{0.408 \Delta(R_n - G) + \gamma \frac{C_n}{T + 273} (e_s - e_a) u_2}{\Delta + \gamma(1 + C_d u_2)} \quad (4.2)$$

where

T = mean daily or hourly air temperature at 1.5 to 2.5m height [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]

u_2 = mean daily or hourly wind speed at 2 m height [m/s]

C_n = Numerator constant, changes according to reference type and time step [K mm $\text{s}^3/\text{Mg/d}$ or K mm $\text{s}^3/\text{Mg/hr}$]

C_d = Denominator constant, changes according to reference type and time step [s/m]

Table 1 gives the Values for C_n and C_d for different reference types and time steps of calculation.

Table 4.1: Values for C_n and C_d in Equation 4.2 (Walter et al., 2005)

Calculation time step	Short Reference ET_{os}		Tall Reference ET_{rs}		Units for ET_{os} , ET_{rs}	Units for R_n , G
	C_n	C_d	C_n	C_d		
Daily	900	0.34	1600	0.38	mm/d	MJ/m ² /d
Hourly during daytime	37	0.24	66	0.25	mm/hr	MJ/m ² /hr
Hourly during nighttime	37	0.96	66	1.7	mm/hr	MJ/m ² /hr

4.4 Methodology and Data

Our primary aim was to estimate the Penman-Monteith ET for *Parthenium hysterophorus* for given input conditions and then compare it with the standardised reference ET for both, the tall and short crops as given by the ASCE. The weather parameters were based on the data collected at the Automatic Weather Station in IIT Kanpur campus. The coordinates of Kanpur (26.4607° N, 80.3334° E, 126m above sea level) were common to all computations. The height of measurement of wind speed, humidity and air temperature measurements was taken as 1.5m above the ground.

The two time periods of the predictions were July 16, 2013 to July 29, 2013 (for the summer stand) and October 1, 2013 to December 15, 2013 (for the winter stand).

4.4 Input Data

The temperature and humidity data were taken from the measurements done at IIT Kanpur, and solar radiation was derived from the temperature data. Wind speed data were used from the website of the Indian Metereological Department (IMD), for the same periods.

4.4.1 Temperature

Temperature measurements were available for every 15 minutes during the periods of study. Daily maximum and minimum temperatures were reported in the data, while all entries for a day were averaged to estimate mean daily temperature. Saturation vapour pressure was computed as a function of the temperature extremes during the day.

$$e_s = \frac{e^o(T_{max}) + e^o(T_{min})}{2} \quad (4.3)$$

where

$$e^o(T) = 0.6108 \exp \left[\frac{17.27T}{T + 237.3} \right] \quad (4.4)$$

where

T = temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]

T_{max} = maximum temperature during the day [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]

T_{min} = minimum temperature during the day [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]

4.4.2 Relative Humidity

Similar to temperature, maximum and minimum daily RH were extracted directly from the measurements, and averaged over the duration of a day to estimate mean RH values. Actual vapour pressure was calculated using both temperature and RH data using the following equation:

$$e_a = 0.6108 \exp \left[\frac{17.27T}{T + 237.3} \right] (RH) \quad (4.5)$$

where

e_a = actual vapour pressure of air [kPa]

T = mean daily temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]

RH = relative humidity [expressed as fraction]

4.4.3 Wind speed

Wind speed data were obtained from an AWS in Allahabad available on the IMD website. The average wind speed at 10 m was estimated by performing component averaging, taking into account the wind direction. For the standardized equations, u_2 (wind speed at a height of 2m) was calculated using the following equation:

$$u_z = u_z \frac{4.87}{\log(67.8 Z_w - 5.42)} \quad (4.6)$$

where

u_z = wind speed at the height of 2m [m/s]

u_z = wind speed at height of z metres [m/s]

Z_w = height at which wind speed measurements were taken ($Z_w = 10\text{m}$) [m]

4.4.4 Solar Radiation

Due to the dearth of directly measured radiation data, net radiation (R_n) was estimated using measured temperature data, as follows:

$$R_n = R_{ns} - R_{nl} \quad (4.7)$$

where

R_n = Net radiation [$\text{MJ}/\text{m}^2/\text{d}$]

R_{ns} = Net shortwave radiation, defined as positive downwards [$\text{MJ}/\text{m}^2/\text{d}$]

R_{nl} = Net longwave radiation, defined as positive upwards [$\text{MJ}/\text{m}^2/\text{d}$]

Net shortwave radiation (R_{ns}) is the difference between the incoming solar radiation and the reflected solar radiation:

$$R_{ns} = R_s(1 - \alpha) \quad (4.8)$$

where

R_s = incoming shortwave radiation [$\text{MJ}/\text{m}^2/\text{d}$]

α = albedo or canopy reflection coefficient (= 0.23 for standardized short and tall reference surfaces) [dimensionless]

R_s is estimated using the Hargreaves-Samani radiation prediction formula (Hargreaves and Samani 1982):

$$R_s = k_{RS} \sqrt{(T_{max} - T_{min})} R_a \quad (4.9)$$

where

R_a = Extraterrestrial radiation [MJ/m²/d]

T_{max} = maximum air temperature [°C]

T_{min} = minimum air temperature [°C]

k_{RS} = adjustment coefficient (0.16 for 'interior' locations where the local land mass dominates and no large body impacts air masses) [°C^{-0.5}]

Extraterrestrial radiation (R_a) by definition is the short-wave radiation, taken in the absence of an atmosphere, and is a function of the day (of the year), time of day, and latitude.

$$R_a = \frac{24}{\pi} G_{sc} d_r [\omega_s \sin(\phi) \sin(\delta) + \cos(\phi) \cos(\delta) \sin(\omega_s)] \quad (4.10)$$

where

G_{sc} = solar constant [4.92 MJ/m²/hr]

d_r = inverse relative distance factor (squared) for earth-sun [dimensionless]

ω_s = sunset hour angle [radians]

ϕ = latitude (= 26.4607° i.e. 0.461826337 radians) [radians]

δ = solar declination [radians]

d_r and δ are calculated as follows:

$$d_r = 1 + 0.033 \cos \left[\frac{2\pi}{365} J \right] \quad (4.11)$$

and

$$\delta = 0.409 \sin \left[\frac{2\pi}{365} J - 1.39 \right] \quad (4.12)$$

where

J = number of the day of the year between 1 and 365 or 366 (depending on whether the year of study is a leap year)

The sunset hour angle (ω_s) is given by

$$\omega_s = \arccos[-\tan(\phi)\tan(\delta)] \quad (4.13)$$

The longwave radiation (R_{nl}) which is the difference between the longwave radiation from the surface upwards and from the sky downwards, is given by:

$$R_{nl} = \sigma f_{cd} (0.34 - 0.14\sqrt{e_a}) \left[\frac{T_{Kmax}^4 + T_{Kmin}^4}{2} \right] \quad (4.14)$$

where

R_{nl} = net longwave radiation [MJ/m²/d]

σ = Stefan-Boltzmann constant [4.901 x 10⁻⁹ MJ K⁻⁴ m⁻²/d]

f_{cd} = cloudiness function [dimensionless]

e_a = actual vapour pressure [kPa]

T_{Kmax} = maximum absolute temperature during the day [K]

T_{Kmin} = minimum absolute temperature during the day [K]

The cloudiness function, f_{cd} (limited between 0.05 and 1.0) is given by

$$f_{cd} = 1.35 \frac{R_s}{R_{so}} - 0.35 \quad (4.15)$$

where

R_s/R_{so} = relative solar radiation (ranges between 0.3 and 1.0)

R_s = measured or calculated solar radiation [MJ/m²/d]

R_{so} = calculated clear sky radiation [MJ/m²/d]

If the clear sky radiation is unavailable, we can use the following computation, for the purposes of calculating R_n :

$$R_{so} = (0.75 + 2 \times 10^{-5}z)R_a \quad (4.16)$$

where z = station elevation above sea level (=136m, as Kanpur is 126m above sea level and a standard AWS is 10m above the ground level) [m]

4.4.5 Plant parameters

The ASCE Penman-Monteith equation requires the input of 3 plant based parameters for ET computation – average height of vegetation (m), leaf area index (LAI) and effective stomatal resistance (r_l). These three were the only inputs which varied across the different crops/plants studied.

For *Parthenium*, LAI and mean height of vegetation (given in Table 4.2) were reported from observed/computed values in (Pandey et al. 2003), corresponding to their winter stand (October-December 1997-1998). The stomatal resistance, r_l , for *Parthenium* was approximated as 169.95 s/m, using measurements reported in the same source.

Table 4.2: Leaf Area Index, height of vegetation and stomatal resistance for *Parthenium* (Pandey, 2003)

	Summer (May-Jul)		Winter (Oct – Dec)	
	1997 (Y1)	1998 (Y2)	1997 (Y1)	1998 (Y2)
Year of study/experiment	1997 (Y1)	1998 (Y2)	1997 (Y1)	1998 (Y2)
LAI (m ² / m ²)	5.64	5.89	3.38	3.60
Mean LAI (m ² / m ²)	5.76		3.49	
Height of vegetation (m)	1.779	1.730	0.148	0.157
Mean height of vegetation (m)	1.755		0.152	
Stomatal resistance (s/m)	169.95		169.95	

For Durum wheat, LAI and mean plant height were reported from (Acevedo et al. 1991) corresponding to the mean seasonal temperature of 20.7°C, which was closest to the mean daily temperature of our study period, 21.3°C. The stomatal resistance, r_1 , used in the study was the average of r_1 from different varieties of durum wheat reported by Rees et al. (1993).

Table 4.3: Mean height of the vegetation, Leaf area index, and Stomatal resistance r_1 for Durum Wheat (Acevedo, et. al 1991 and Rees et. al 1993) and Maize (corn) (ArcSWAT Land cover – Plant database)

	Mean vegetation height (m)	LAI (m ² /m ²)	Stomatal resistance r_1 (s/m)
Durum Wheat	0.576	2.7	87.6
Maize (corn)	2.5	6	142.86

For maize, LAI and mean plant height were reported from the Land Cover database provided in the ArcSWAT program, and is given in Table 4.3.

4.5 Procedure of estimating ET

1. The slope of the Saturation Vapour pressure-Temperature curve (Δ) was given by:

$$\Delta = \frac{2503 \exp\left(\frac{17.27T}{T + 237.3}\right)}{(T + 237.3)^2} \quad (4.17)$$

where T = mean daily temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]

The psychrometric constant (γ) was computed as a function of the atmospheric pressure:

$$P = 101.3 \left(\frac{293 - 0.0065z}{293}\right)^{5.26} \quad (4.18)$$

$$\gamma = 0.000665 P \quad (4.19)$$

where P = atmospheric pressure at the AWS [kPa]

z = height of the AWS above mean sea level [m]

2. Solar heat flux density (G), being the thermal energy utilized for heating the soil, beneath fully vegetated grass is relatively small in comparison with R_n , and thus was ignored, so that $G = 0 \text{ MJ/m}^2\text{d}$
3. The aerodynamic resistance (r_a), was applied for neutral stability conditions, as:

$$r_a = \frac{\ln \left[\frac{z_w - d}{z_{om}} \right] + \ln \left[\frac{z_h - d}{z_{oh}} \right]}{k^2 u_z} \quad (4.20)$$

where

z_w = height of wind measurements [m]

z_h = height of humidity and air temperature measurements [m]

d = zero plane displacement height = $0.67h$ [m]

z_{om} = roughness length governing momentum transfer = $0.123h$ [m]

z_{oh} = roughness length governing transfer of heat and vapour = $0.0123h$ [m]

k = von Karman's constant = 0.41 [dimensionless]

u_z = wind speed at height z [m/s]

h = mean height of vegetation [m]

4. It was initially understood that Equation (1) would be used to calculate ET for *Parthenium* and Durum wheat and Equation (2) would be used for the standardized reference ET (for both tall and short reference crops). However the conception behind the use of the standardized Penman-Monteith equation is not that the grasses are meant to be benchmarked against, but rather to infer that the procedure for computation is standard (Walter et al. 2005). Also, we did not have any paucity of weather input parameters (for instance the standardized reference PM equation demands a calculation according to wind speeds measured at a height of 2m, but since we already had true measurements at a different height which could be used in (1), it would have left more room for error if (2) was used with height corrections). Thus it was decided to measure the ET without Equation (2), i.e. by estimating ET using Equation (1) using known/approximated plant parameters, for the periods of

16th July – 29th July 2013 and 1st October – 15th December 2013. The K_{time} corresponding to the daily time step (= 86400 s/d) was used for the computations.

4.6 Results

The Penman-Monteith equation is a physical equation which estimates the response of ET to the interplay of the changing weather based upon the inputs of temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, and solar radiation. More relative humidity results in a decreased vapour pressure deficit leading to decreased ET. The solar radiation is related to the amount of energy available for evapotranspiration processes. Thus a higher level of solar radiation results in more soil evaporation and plant transpiration. Wind, on the other hand, increases vapour pressure deficit by replacing more humid surrounding air by drier air and thus enhances ET. Temperature is affected by the incoming solar radiation as well as the long-wave radiation emitted by the earth, and exerts a strong influence on the ET rate. However, since these input factors were the same for all our plant types (*Parthenium*, Wheat, Maize, Tall and short Reference) it was expected that ET would respond in similar ways for the same set of inputs conditions.

The effect of different plant parameters on ET was of primary importance in this study as these varied across plant types. Stomatal conductance and LAI (both contributing to the r_1 term), and mean height of vegetation were the only parameters which varied across the plant types.

Table 4.4: Plant parameters of the plant types used in study

	<i>Parthenium</i>		Durum Wheat (<i>rabi</i> crop)	Maize (<i>kharif</i> crop)	Tall Reference	Short Reference
	Summer	Winter				
Mean height of vegetation (m)	0.152	1.755	0.576	2.5	0.5	0.12
Surface resistance (s/m)	48.95		32.44	23.81	70	45

The mean height of vegetation is involved in the computation of aerodynamic resistance (r_a). A taller plant faces, in general, lesser aerodynamic resistance, and thus transpires more. Surface resistance is a similar term which combines the ability of a plant to transpire through the stomata (stomatal resistance r_l), and the spread of the plant on the ground (LAI). Thus, a higher surface resistance term would also lead to a lower ET.

Figure 4.1: Comparing Evapotranspiration across plant types (without ASCE standardization) for Winter stand (Oct-Dec 2013)

The estimates obtained from the Penman Monteith method yielded results along the estimated lines. In the winter stand, durum wheat had the maximum mean height and least surface resistance, and hence had the highest ET rates (Figure 4.1). The tall reference grass had an advantage over both *Parthenium* and the short reference grass on account of its height, but the surface resistances of the latter two were lesser, leading to mixed ET responses. Also, *Parthenium* and the short reference grass had similar ET characteristics owing to their similar plant input parameters (Figure 4.1).

Figure 4.2: Comparing Evapotranspiration across plant types (without ASCE standardization) for Summer stand (July 2013)

In the summer stand, the first observation was that the ET values were relatively higher than the winter stand, because of higher average temperatures and subsequently higher average solar radiation, which was generated using temperature data. In summer, the tallest crop was maize (which was taller than *Parthenium* by about 43%) and it had higher ET losses primarily due to lower r_a values. The relatively lower r_s term also contributed to the higher ET estimates for maize. The discrepancy from around the 21st to 23rd July was because of the unusually low wind speeds on those days, which reduced the advantage of the height, as both height and wind speed contribute to the aerodynamic resistance term, and the effect of abnormally low winds overpowered the height advantage for both maize and *Parthenium*.

4.7 Limitations of the study

The application of Penman Monteith Equation had the following limitations:

1. Stomatal conductance is a parameter which is inherently difficult to measure because of difficulty in taking measurements at leaf scale. Approximations were made from the literature which have uncertainties owing to non-homogeneity of conditions in which measurements were made (across the crops).
2. Stomatal conductance for crops was taken as a constant for a particular crop, although it is known to change daily – because of physiological feedback processes. These dynamic changes were not accounted for in the study.
3. The study used plant mean heights reported in the literature. However, ideally carefully measured values from stands exposed to the same weather, soil properties and water availability should have been used, especially, since the height is a vital term in computing the aerodynamic resistance.

Chapter 5

Hydrologic Modeling of a River Basin

5.1 Introduction

A hydrological model is a mathematical representation of the physical processes taking place within the hydrologic cycle. These processes can include the various components of water balance like surface runoff, evapotranspiration, subsurface flow, and lateral flow or link the hydrosphere with other earth system components such as the biosphere, atmosphere and lithosphere and relevant processes taking place within their domains. Hydrological models can be applied to spatially and temporally extrapolate point measurements, improve the fundamental understanding of current hydrological systems, assess the impact of land-cover change or climate change on water resources and develop new models or improve old models for management decisions related to current and future catchment hydrology (for instance irrigation water management, groundwater management, streamflow restoration, flood forecasting and management, and water quality evaluation) (Pechlivanidis et al. 2011).

5.2 Motivation and Objectives

There are inherent spatial and temporal limitations in conducting laboratory scale transpiration experiments on plants and using their results to predict the effect of land cover changes (representing a *Parthenium* infestation) at catchment scales. The Penman Monteith Method can be used to predict ET (refer to Chapter 4), but falls short when a more comprehensive analysis of the effect of *Parthenium* on other aspects of water balance has to be undertaken. Additionally, a wider analysis taking into account the effect of land cover

change on all major water balance components and relevant aspects of related systems is a prerequisite for any attempt to manage and mitigate the problem of the spread of such an invasive alien species.

The major objectives of hydrological modelling are:

- (i) To study the effect of an invasion by *Parthenium hysterophorus* on major water balance components of a representative sub-basin in the Ganga, using a suitable hydrological model.
- (ii) To run the same model for periods of extreme climatic conditions – drought years and excess rainfall years, which would help gain a better understanding of how *Parthenium* responds to extreme growth conditions and how its effects on water balance components compare with relatively moderate years.

5.3 Criteria for Selecting a Suitable Model

There are a few criteria which had to be followed for the selection of a suitable model for the study:

- The model should be based on physical equations and should be able to simulate water balance processes at a basin scale.
- The model should be able to incorporate plant growth parameters in appropriate detail, so that model outputs dependent on land cover, such as evapotranspiration, could be predicted.

- The accuracy of model predictions should have been tested for performance, especially for agricultural basins, so as to be useful to draw conclusions on the effect of *Parthenium* invasions in agricultural areas.

A comparison of models such as the Dynamic Watershed Simulation Model (DWSM) (Borah and Bera 2004), SWAT model and the Hydrologic Simulation Program – Fortran (HSPF) (Bicknell et al. 1997), has been carried out by Borah and Bera (2003, 2004). This comparison was done on the basis that in all these models, hydrologic processes, sediment circulation and chemical processes are computed by dividing the catchment areas into smaller basic sub-catchments. These studies conclude that the SWAT model shows promise especially for long-term simulations in primarily agricultural basins.

Thus the SWAT model was chosen for the study.

5.4 The SWAT Model

5.4.1 History and Introduction of SWAT

The Soil and Water Assessment Tool model (Arnold and Fohrer 2005; Arnold et al. 1998) is a semi-distributed, continuous time, basin scale, physically based hydrological model, and has been effective in assessing multi-scale and multi-environment water resource and non-point source pollution related problems (Gassman et al. 2007). Its development is a result of a continuing USDA Agricultural Research Service (ARS) experience in modeling spanning over 30 years. Origins of SWAT can be found in USDA-ARS models such as Chemicals, Runoff and Erosion from Agricultural Management Systems (CREAMS) model (Knisel 1980), the Groundwater Loading Effects on Agricultural Management Systems (GLEAMS) model (Leonard et al. 1987), and the Environment Impact Policy Climate

(EPIC) model (Izaurre et al. 2006). The current form of the SWAT model is a direct successor to the Simulator for Water Resources in Rural Basins (SWRRB) model (Arnold and Williams 1987) which was used for simulation of the impacts of management on water and sediment movement on ungauged U.S. rural basins.

5.4.2 Model Overview

The SWAT model uses physical patterns in describing the circulation of water, sediments and nutrients, and plant growth, by applying the required data on climate, terrain topography, vegetation distribution, soil characteristics and land use of the river basin, to be input by the user. It can be used for long-term simulations, but is not designed for detailed simulations of extreme events such as flood wave episodes (Simić et al. 2009).

The SWAT model divides the catchment into multiple sub-basins, which are further divided into the smallest unit of computations used by SWAT, the hydrologic response units (HRUs), which have a unique combination of land use, vegetation and soil characteristics. SWAT uses five linear reservoirs for the transport of water and other hydrological entities: vegetation cover reservoir, snow accumulation and melting reservoir, surface reservoir, underground reservoir and surface runoff reservoir (Simić et al. 2009). A complete hydrological balance at the HRU level includes the accumulation and evaporation of intercepted rainwater on the canopy, subsequently computing the effective rainfall to the ground, a water exchange between the soil layer and surface runoff, after which the remaining water is distributed as evapotranspiration, sub-surface flow, underground flow, and water storage. The remaining water penetrates into deepest reservoirs and is considered lost from the system. The water balance is explained in more detail in the next section.

The hydrological simulations can be divided into two groups of processes:

1. The Soil/Land Phase of the hydrologic cycle in which the processes on the soil and sub-surface soil occur along with the circulation of nutrients, sediment and pesticides.
2. The Routing Phase of the hydrologic cycle, in which the circulation of water and sediment occurs through the river network to the outlet of the unit of computation.

5.4.3 Water Balance in SWAT Model

SWAT Water Balance Reservoirs

A flowchart of the linear reservoir system used by SWAT is given in Figure 5.1. The containers represent the reservoirs and the arrows represent the fluxes between them.

Figure 9.1: Linear Reservoir System in SWAT (Simić et al. 2009)

Reservoir 1 represents the canopy cover that the precipitation first comes into contact with, before making contact with the soil surface. The intercepted rainfall goes through a combination of canopy storage (which depends on the maximum capacity for canopy interception (can_{day}) of the vegetation), evaporation (E_a) and the balance rainfall is the effective rainfall (R) which falls to the soil surface.

Reservoir 2 is for snowfall, which may either sublimate (E_{sub}) or melt as snowmelt (SNO_{melt}), and join the effective rainfall from Reservoir 1.

Reservoir 3 is the unsaturated soil layer, also known as the vadose zone, extending from the soil surface to the saturated underground aquifer zone. The soil layer(s) may have water

content ranging between the wilting point (WP) and the field capacity (FC), above which the water becomes excess soil moisture (SW_{excess}) and may either flow out as surface runoff (Q'_{surf}), be evaporated (E_{ground}) or seep lower into the saturated aquifer system through percolation of bypass flow (w_{seep}). The outlets of the preceding two reservoirs (R and $SNOMelt$) are the inlets for this reservoir.

Reservoir 4 is the underground aquifer system where once the height of the water table (h_{wtbl}) can exceed the maximum water table height (h_{wtbl}^{max}), the excess water contributes to the streamflow as base or return flow (Q_{gw}).

Reservoir 5 represents the surface runoff reservoir which details the retention capacity of surface and immediately underlying soil layer.

SWAT Water Balance Equation

Irrespective of the problem being analysed, the basic mechanism of the SWAT model is the simulation of the hydrological cycle, based on the following water balance:

$$SW_t = SW_o + \sum_{i=1}^t (R_{day,i} - Q_{surf,i} - w_{seep,i} - E_{a,i} - Q_{gw,i}) \quad (\text{Equation 5.1})$$

where

SW_t = soil moisture at time t [mm]

SW_o = soil moisture at the beginning of the time step [mm]

$R_{day,i}$ = precipitation (including snowfall) for i th day [mm]

$Q_{surf,i}$ = surface runoff for the i th day [mm]

$w_{seep,i}$ = seepage of water from the soil into deeper layers on the i th day [mm]

$E_{a,i}$ = evapotranspiration on the i th day [mm]

$Q_{gw,i}$ = underground runoff during the i th day [mm]

t = time of simulation [days]

Equation 5.1. is also represented in Figure 5.2.

Figure 5.2: Fluxes contributing to water balance of the Unsaturated Soil reservoir

5.5 Study Area

The Punpun river basin was chosen as the study area in which the SWAT model was to be simulated. The Punpun is a tributary of the Ganga, and it originates in Palamu district (Jharkhand) on the Chota Nagpur plateau and flows through the districts of Aurangabad, Gaya, Jahanabad to meet the Ganga at Fatuha ($25^{\circ}30'49''$, $85^{\circ}18'12''$). Its major tributaries are Batane, Kalan, Madar, Adri, (in the head reach) and Morhar and Darhar (in the lower reach). A map depicting the location of the Punpun basin is given in Figure 5.3.

Figure 5.3: The Punpun River Basin

The outlet of the river basin for this study is Sripalpur ($25^{\circ}30'6''$, $85^{\circ}18'12''$), since the Central Water Commission (CWC) has set up a gauging site here, which is one of the three gauging sites in the basin.

Most of the river basin (around 74%) is constituted by agricultural land. Crops like rice, maize, pulses and wheat are mainly grown here, apart from non-food crops like oil seeds and vegetables. The remaining land cover mostly consists of deciduous forests (~5%) and about 3% settlement areas.

The choice of the Punpun river basin for the study was influenced by the fact that it has a primarily agricultural land cover. The land cover was a key factor because *Parthenium*

has reportedly decreased crop yield by upto 40% in India(Khosla and Sobti 1981). In addition, since it has a high potential for dispersal and its removal from farmlands is labour and cost intensive, it becomes more important to model and subsequently study a *Parthenium* invasion on the agricultural land cover of the Punpun river basin.

The Punpun is mainly rain-fed, and a highly meandering river. It has little water during the dry period, and most of the rainfall in the basin occurs during the monsoon period (June-September).

5.6 Data Used

5.6.1 Digital Elevation Model File

The Digital Elevation Model (DEM) is a 3D representation of a terrain's surface. It is created from the elevation data which can be obtained from topographic maps, theodolite or total stations, real-time kinematic GPS (Global Positioning System), Doppler radar, surveying and mapping drones, interferometry from radar data and techniques such as LIDAR, stereo photogrammetry from aerial surveys, inertial surveys and range imaging (Li et al. 2005). Preparation is done frequently using remote sensing rather than direct survey data. A DEM can be represented by a raster (a dot matrix data structure which represents an array or grid of pixels, and each pixel has a value associated with it). The DEM file used for the study is given in Figure 5.4.

**Figure 5.4: DEM raster file and Drainage shape file used:
The elevation is shown by a gradient from higher elevation (lighter colour)
to lower elevation (darker colour)**

The DEM was obtained from the website of the Ganga River Basin Management Plan (GRBMP) website (<http://gisserver.civil.iitd.ac.in/grbmp/>).

5.6.2 Drainage Data

Drainage data available on the GRBMP website as a shape file (a popular geospatial vector data format used for geographic information systems or GIS). They are developed by the Environmental Systems Research Institute (ESRI) for compatibility of data between ESRI and other GIS software products and spatially describe vector features like points, lines or polygons. The Drainage shapefile used is given in Figure 5.4.

5.6.3 Land Use Land Cover (LULC) Data

The land use raster used, which was downloaded from the GRBMP website, was based on the dataset developed by the National Remote Sensing Centre (NRSC), Indian Space Research Organisation (ISRO). It primarily consisted of agricultural land (about 74%), which was distributed between *Kharif*, *Rabi*, *Zaid* and Double/Triple crops (irrigated by surface water, ground water, or conjunctive use). Barren land covered about 15% of the land cover, and the rest was divided among deciduous and mixed forests, range brushes and range grasses. The LULC of the Punpun river basin is given in Figure 5.8.

5.6.4 Soil Data

Soil data was based on the raster dataset prepared by the NRSC and National Bureau of Soil Survey (NBSS) prepared for the GRBMP. The major soil classes ranged from a Sand-Silt-Clay ratio of about 51-31-18 (%) to 29-54-17 (%). The soil map is given in Figure 5.5.

Figure 5.5: Soil Characterisation of the Punpun river basin

5.6.5 IMD Gridded Weather Data

Input weather data, prepared by the IMD, was used for the SWAT simulations. IMD has gridded rainfall data at both $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ and $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ spatial resolutions. For this study, temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$), precipitation (mm), wind speed (m/s), and solar radiation ($\text{MJ}/\text{m}^2/\text{day}$) data corresponding to the Sripalpur station were used. Relative humidity was simulated by the SWAT model. The IMD Precipitation data were derived from the Asian Precipitation – Highly Resolved Observational Data Integration Towards Evaluation (APHRODITE) of Water Resources database, with a resolution of $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$. Daily rainfall dataset was available from 1948 to 2007. The IMD data for daily maximum and minimum temperature, wind speed and solar radiation were based on the Princeton University weather database, with a resolution of $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ and available from 1961 to 2007. The coordinates for the weather stations are given in Table 5.1. The gridded data points are given in Figure 5.6.

Figure 5.6: Monitoring Stations (Weather inputs and discharge) for Punpun river basin

5.7.6 Observed Discharge Data

Daily observed Discharge data (in m³/s or cumecs) was available from the Central Water Commission (CWC) stations, prepared for the GRBMP. Out of the 3 stations in the basin, Sripalpur was chosen, as daily data were available from 1959 onwards, and the other 2 stations were active for only 5 months every year. Details regarding the CWC station (Sripalpur) used for discharge data are given in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1: CWC Gauge Station and IMD Weather monitoring Stations used for simulation

S. No.	Station	Data available for	Latitude	Longitude	Data available from
1.	Sripalpur	Daily discharge (cumecs)	25°30'6"	85°18'12"	1959
2.	AP101162 (APHRODITE)	Precipitation (mm)	25°22'30"	84° 52' 30"	1961
3.	85502550 (Princeton University)	All weather inputs apart from precipitation	25° 30' 0"	85° 30' 0"	1948

5.7 SWAT Model Setup

5.7.1 Modeling Framework

Different SWAT simulations were run to model the gradual increase of *Parthenium* cover in the Punpun river basin, with an aim to establish near-representative conditions of the study area. These simulations were run for 3 simulation periods characterizing moderate, wet and dry years, which were established using available rainfall data from the APHRODITE database. The annual rainfall hydrograph from 1961 to 2007 is given in Figure 5.7.

Figure 5.7: Yearly rainfall (mm/yr) from 1961-1999, extracted from APHRODITE's water resources database

The average annual rainfall from during the 1961-2007 period was 908.9 mm/yr. The 10 year period of 1990-1999 was designated as the time period of moderate rainfall. This period had an average annual precipitation of 868.5 mm/yr, which although was lower than the 1961-2007 average and had no missing discharge. The 5 year period from 1966-1970 was chosen as the period of dry conditions, with an average annual rainfall of 703.2 mm/yr. The 5 year period from 1984-1988 was chosen as the period of wet conditions, with an average annual rainfall of 1140.1 mm/yr.

The nomenclatures for the scenarios used for modeling along with their descriptions are given on the next page.

1. Normal Period (1990-1999):

- (i) Base: This is the scenario in which the existing LULC of the Punpun basin was used, and the observed discharge values could be used to check the accuracy of the model predictions. The land cover is illustrated in Figure 5.8.

Figure 5.8: LULC Map of Punpun River Basin without *Parthenium*, for Base (Base, D-Base and W-Base) scenarios (mostly agricultural land)

- (ii) S1: This is a hypothetical scenario in which all the barren land of the Punpun river basin has been invaded by *Parthenium hysterophorus*. This is a very plausible situation considering the adaptability of *Parthenium* to different soil and weather conditions. The new land cover is given in Figure 5.9.

Figure 5.9: LULC Map of Punpun River Basin, for S1, D-S1, W-S1 scenarios (Barren land invaded by *Parthenium hysterophorus*)

- (iii) S2: This is another hypothetical scenario in which about one-third of the agricultural land cover has been infested by *Parthenium*, increasing the total *Parthenium* land cover to about half (43%) of the whole river basin. The raster points (areas) of the agricultural land cover which have been newly infested have been chosen randomly, which is not particularly a concern as *Parthenium* doesn't have a strict pattern of growth on an agricultural field. The land cover for scenario S2 is illustrated in Figure 5.10.

Figure 5.10: LULC Map of Punpun River Basin, for S2, D-S2, W-S2 scenarios (Half of the basin invaded by *Parthenium hysterophorus*)

- (iv) S3: This is a hypothetical extreme case, in which all the agricultural land, in addition to the barren land, has undergone a *Parthenium* invasion. This was modelled specifically to understand the extent of the effect of a *Parthenium* invasion on a representative river basin. The land cover illustrations are given in Figure 5.11.

**Figure 5.11: LULC Map of Punpun River Basin, for S3, D-S3, W-S3 scenarios
(All of the basin agricultural and barren land invaded by *Parthenium hysterophorus*)**

2. Dry Period (1966-1970):

These simulations are important to predict the growth of *Parthenium* in highly challenging conditions in which other plant species experience much higher water stress, and for longer periods, than the Normal Period. This is also important to study the effect of its spread on the water balance during the same period.

1. D-Base: This case is similar to the Base scenario of the Normal period. LULC distribution also remains the same.
2. D-S1: This is similar to the S1 case of the Normal period, in which the barren land is invaded by *Parthenium hysterophorus*. LULC distribution remains the same as that of scenario S1.
3. D-S2: This case represents the S2 scenario modelled in the dry years of 1966-1970. LULC remains the same as that of scenario S2.
4. D-S3: This scenario represents an extreme *Parthenium* infestation during dry climatic conditions. LULC of D-S3 remains the same as that of scenario S3.

3. Wet Period (1984-1988):

These simulations were carried out to predict the effect of *Parthenium* invasions during a period of 5 wet years. This included the disastrous floods of 1987, which resulted in agricultural losses worth about Rs. 68,000 lakhs, apart from the deaths of about 1400 persons and 5000 animals in the state of Bihar. (Flood-Report-2012).

1. W-Base: This case is similar to the Base and D-Base cases, assuming that the LULC has not substantially changed between 1966 and 1999.
2. W-S1: This scenario is similar to scenarios S1 and D-S1.
3. W-S2: This case is similar to scenarios S2 and D-S2.
4. W-S3: This scenario is similar to S3 and D-S3, in which *Parthenium* has invaded all the agricultural land cover.

5.7.2 Model Setup

The ArcSWAT add-on for ArcGIS, a GIS interface developed by ESRI, was used to run the SWAT model simulations for all the mentioned scenarios. In the scenarios for the Normal period (Base, S1, S2 and S3), a warm-up period of 2 years was specified out of the 10 years (1990-1999). In the extreme weather scenarios, no warm up period was specified. The model setup had the following:

1. Watershed Delineation:

The purpose of Watershed Delineation is to segment the watersheds into hydrologically connected sub-watersheds for the SWAT model. The delineation process required a DEM in the ESRI grid format. A stream network available as a polyline shapefile (from the GRBMP database) was also burned into the DEM, though it was optional for delineation. After carrying out an automatic DEM based stream preprocessing to compute the flow direction and flow accumulation, an outlet had to be specified for the final delineation. Sripalpur was chosen as the outlet of the watershed, since observed discharge data was available for that particular station, and the watershed was delineated.

2. Hydraulic Response Unit (HRU) Analysis

The HRU analysis is a process of characterizing each sub-basin into smaller units of uniform land use, soil and slope classes, called HRUs, using the ArcSWAT HRU Analysis menu commands.

The land use classes were defined using the NRSC land use raster file. The *kharif*, *rabi*, *zaid* and double/triple conjunctive crops were classified into a single pre-defined LU class called Agricultural land generic (AGRL). This was based on the assumption that agricultural land was randomly invaded by *Parthenium* irrespective of the type of crop that was being cultivated on it.

The Soil Classification was done using the NRSC–NBSS soil data, and specific soil parameters were either chosen from the pre-existing ArcSWAT Soil database, or added to the database using the NRSC-NBSS tables. The soil characterization map and details regarding soil classes is given in Section 5.7.4.

The slope classes were decided using the median value of the slope that computed using the DEM raster dataset, so that the watershed was divided roughly into two slope classes. The median value was 0.8%, and hence two slope classes were made, one which had gentler slopes (less than 0.8%) and one which had steeper slopes (greater than 0.8%).

The HRU definition command was then used to sub-divide the subbasins further into smaller, more unique homogenous units, called HRUs, using a set of specified criteria. The thresholds help in increasing accuracy of predictions and reflect differences in ET and other components for different land covers and soils, giving a better physical portrayal of water balance (Winchell et al. 2007). The multiple HRU option was chosen, and using different

thresholds for land use category, soil type and slope class, multiple HRUs were assigned to a single subbasin. The thresholds used are given in Table 5.2

Table 5.2: HRU definition Thresholds (% of total area) applied in series

Land Use Category Threshold	Soil Type Threshold	Slope Class Threshold
10%	10%	10%

The thresholds are applied by SWAT in series, i.e. all those land use categories which occupied more than 10% of the subbasin area, were assigned to one HRU, and within each new HRU formed, all those soil types which covered more than 10% of the area of the HRU, were assigned a new HRU, and so on. The reasoning behind the choice of thresholds was to try and maintain a balance between enhancing the model accuracy and preventing the model from becoming numerically cumbersome, with consideration given to the accuracy of the available data.

3. Weather Data Import

Details about weather stations used for precipitation input (APHRODITE) and temperature, wind speed and solar radiation input (Princeton University) are given in Table 5.1. Daily measured data were used for all the simulations. Relative humidity data were simulated by the SWAT model, as the measurements were not available.

4. Plant growth/plant cover database

Keeping in mind the basic premise of the SWAT simulations (of analyzing the effect of changing land cover on water balance components), the SWAT plant growth database had to be updated to include the plant parameters of *Parthenium*. The agricultural land was

assigned the AGRL (Agricultural Land Generic) land cover category, as mentioned earlier. Since *Parthenium* is not included in the SWAT plant database, its parameters had to be extracted from the literature available. More weightage was given to the parameters which were involved in water balance, as compared to the parameters which were used by the model to compute other bio-chemical variables like content of Nitrogen, Phosphorus and other chemicals, crop yield (of *Parthenium*) etc. which were not directly relevant to our purpose. A description of the parameters along with their values from literature used for the SWAT model is given in Table 5.3.

Table 5.3: Relevant plant parameters for *Parthenium*, used by the SWAT model

S. No.	Plant parameter	Description	Parameter value	Source
1.	Base Temperature (T_BASE)	The minimum temperature at which plant growth occurs, and below which the plant becomes dormant. Used by SWAT to calculate number of heat units accumulated every day.	7 °C	(Pandey et al. 2003)
2.	Optimal Temperature (T_OPT)	The temperature at which the maximum plant growth, in terms of photosynthetic response. Used by SWAT to calculate temperature stress.	30 °C	(Pandey et al. 2003)
3.	Leaf Area Development related parameters (BLAI, FRGRW1, LAIMX1, FRGRW2, LAIMX2, DLAI)	These parameters are all coordinates of points on the graph plotted between the leaf area index (LAI) and plant growth (measured in terms of potential heat units (PHU), which is called the leaf area development (LAD) curve. Since the LAD	BLAI = 5.89 FRGRW1 = 0.05 LAIMX1 = 1.178 FRGRW2 = 0.2 LAIMX2 = 24.712 DLAI = 0.7	BLAI from (Pandey et al. 2003)

		<p>curve for <i>Parthenium</i> was not available in the literature, it was approximated as shown in Figure 5.12</p> <p>SWAT uses these parameters to compute plant growth and canopy related parameters during the growing season.</p>		
4.	Root depth (RDMX)	Used by SWAT for soil water related computations.	RDMX = 0.39 m	(Dolai et al. 2013)
5.	Canopy height (CHTMX)	Used by SWAT in computing aerodynamic resistance in ET computations.	CHTMX = 1.77m	(Pandey et al. 2003)
6.	Stomatal Conductance (GSI)	A measure of the rate of passage of fluids (water vapour, CO ₂) through the stomata of the leaf. Used by SWAT in the Penman-Monteith calculations of plant ET.	GSI = 0.23 mmol/m ² /s or 0.0056 m/s	(Pandey et al. 2003)

The leaf area development parameters are:

- BLAI – Maximum potential leaf area index for plant/land cover [(kg/ha)/(MJ/m²)]
- FRGRW1 – Fraction of plant growing season or PHU corresponding to first point on LAD curve
- LAIMX1 – Fraction of BLAI corresponding to first point on LAD curve
- FRGRW2 – Fraction of plant growing season or PHU corresponding to second point on LAD curve
- LAIMX2 – Fraction of BLAI corresponding to second point on LAD curve
- DLAI – Fraction of plant/land cover growing season, when leaf area starts to decline

Figure 5.12: Leaf Area Development curve approximated for *Parthenium*

5.8 SWAT Computation of Water Balance components

5.8.1 Surface Runoff

Surface runoff is simulated by SWAT using either the SCS Runoff Curve Number method, or the Green and Ampt Infiltration method. The Green and Ampt Infiltration method assumes that the soil profile is homogenous and antecedent moisture is uniformly distributed in the soil profile, both of which would decrease the accuracy of soil moisture modeling needed for our simulations. Thus it was decided to estimate surface runoff using the SCS Runoff Curve number method using the following equation:

$$Q_{surf} = \frac{(R_{day} - I_a)^2}{(R_{day} - I_a + S)} \quad (\text{Equation 5.2})$$

Q_{surf} = accumulated runoff or rainfall excess [mm]

R_{day} = rainfall depth for the day [mm]

I_a = initial abstractions including surface storage, interception and infiltration prio to Runoff (commonly approximated as $I_a = 0.2S$) [mm]

S = retention parameter, a function of the land use, soil, slope and management, given by:

$$S = 25.4 \left(\frac{1000}{CN} - 10 \right) \quad (\text{Equation 5.3})$$

where

CN = Curve number for a particular combination of soil permeability , land use and antecedent soil water conditions, calculated daily by SWAT

5.8.2 Evapotranspiration (ET)

SWAT calculates ET using a series of steps. The precipitation stored in the canopy, is first removed as part of the initial abstractions included in the calculation of surface runoff using

the SCS Curve Number Runoff calculation. The remaining precipitation then reaches the soil surface and is distributed between plant transpiration and sublimation/soil evaporation. Sublimation only occurs if there is snow cover on the soil surface, which is not applicable to our study, and thus only soil evaporation and plant transpiration processes needed to be analysed.

Plant Transpiration

Initially the Potential Evapotranspiration (PET) is calculated using the Penman Monteith Equation, which has been explained in detail in Section 4.3. This is the total evapotranspirative demand; the actual ET is lesser than the PET depending on the environmental conditions like soil moisture availability. The transpiration by plants depends on the water uptake from soil layers, and the water uptake changes with the availability of soil moisture. The actual uptake, after correcting for soil moisture availability, is transpired by the plant.

$$E_{t,act} = w_{actualup} \quad \text{(Equation 5.4)}$$

where

$E_{t,act}$ = actual amount of daily transpiration [mm]

$w_{actualup}$ = total daily plant water uptake from all layers of the soil [mm]

$$w_{actualup} = \sum_{ly=1}^n w_{actualup,ly} \quad (\text{Equation 5.5})$$

where

$w_{actualup,ly}$ = actual daily water uptake from layer ly of the soil [mm]

n = number of soil layers in soil database

Here, the actual uptake from a soil layer is calculated using the following equation:

$$w_{actualup,ly} = \min[w''_{up,ly}, (SW_{ly} - WP_{ly})] \quad (\text{Equation 5.6})$$

where

$w''_{up,ly}$ = potential water uptake adjusted for initial soil water content [mm]

SW_{ly} = soil water content in the soil layer ly for a particular day [mm]

WP = water content for layer ly , at wilting point [mm]

Wilting point water content is calculated using the bulk density of soil and clay content, and the potential water uptake is calculated as:

$$w''_{up,ly} = \begin{cases} w'_{up,ly} \cdot \exp \left[5 \cdot \left(\frac{SW_{ly}}{25 \cdot AWC_{ly}} - 1 \right) \right] & SW_{ly} < 25 \cdot AWC_{ly} \\ w'_{up,ly} & SW_{ly} \geq 25 \cdot AWC_{ly} \end{cases} \quad (\text{Equation 5.7})$$

where

$w'_{up,ly}$ = adjusted daily potential water uptake for layer ly [mm]

AWC_{ly} = available water capacity for layer ly [mm]

If the upper soil layers cannot provide enough water to meet the potential water uptake, lower layers may be allowed to compensate using the following equation:

$$w'_{up,ly} = w_{up,ly} + w_{demand} \cdot epco \quad (\text{Equation 5.8})$$

where

$w_{up,ly}$ = potential daily water uptake for layer ly [mm]

w_{demand} = water uptake demand not met by the overlying layers [mm]

$epco$ = plant uptake compensation factor

$$W_{up,ly} = W_{up,zl} - W_{up,zu} \quad (\text{Equation 5.9})$$

where

$w_{up,zl}$ = potential water uptake from the lower boundary of the soil layer [mm]

$w_{up,zu}$ = potential water uptake from the upper boundary of the soil layer [mm]

The potential water uptake to any depth is given by:

$$w_{up,z} = \frac{E_t}{[1 - \exp(-\beta_w)]} \left[1 - \exp\left(-\beta_w \cdot \frac{z}{z_{root}}\right) \right] \quad (\text{Equation 5.10})$$

where

E_t = maximum plant transpiration on a given day, using PM equation [mm]

β_w = water-use distribution parameter

z = depth from soil surface [mm]

z_{root} = depth of root development in the soil [mm]

Soil Water Evaporation

Once it is established that a soil water evaporation demand exists, SWAT partitions the evaporative demand between different soil layers:

$$E_{soil,z} = E''_s \frac{z}{z + \exp(2.374 - 0.00713 \cdot z)} \quad (\text{Equation 5.11})$$

where

$E_{soil,z}$ = evaporative demand at z depth [mm]

E''_s = maximum soil water evaporation during a given day [mm]

The coefficients of Equation 5.11. are selected in a way that 50% of the evaporative demand is met by the top 10mm of soil (and 95% is extracted from the top 100mm of soil).

$$E'_{soil,ly} = \begin{cases} E_{soil,ly} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{2.5(SW_{ly} - FC_{ly})}{FC_{ly} - WP_{ly}}\right) & SW_{ly} < FC_{ly} \\ E_{soil,ly} & SW_{ly} \geq FC_{ly} \end{cases} \quad (\text{Equation 5.12})$$

where

$E'_{soil,ly}$ = evaporative demand for layer ly adjusted for water content [mm]

SW_{ly} = soil water content of layer ly [mm]

FC_{ly} = water content at field capacity [mm]

WP_{ly} = water content at wilting point [mm]

Additionally, SWAT allows a maximum of 80% of the plant water available in the soil to be removed on any single day, using the following equation:

$$E''_{soil,ly} = \min[E'_{soil,ly}, 0.8 (SW_{ly} - WP_{ly})] \quad (\text{Equation 5.13})$$

where

$E''_{soil,ly}$ = amount of water removed by evaporation from layer ly [mm]

5.8.3 Groundwater Flow

The contribution of the shallow aquifer to the streamflow is called the base flow or groundwater flow. Base flow can occur only once the water stored in the shallow aquifer exceeds a specified threshold, $aq_{shthr,q}$.

The steady-state response to recharge of the groundwater flow is :

$$Q_{gw} = \frac{8000 \cdot K_{sat}}{L_{gw}^2} \cdot h_{wtbl} \quad (\text{Equation 5.14})$$

where

Q_{gw} = groundwater flow into the main channel on the i th day [mm]

K_{sat} = hydraulic conductivity of the aquifer [mm/day]

L_{gw} = distance from the main channel to the sub-basin divide for the groundwater system [m]

h_{wtbl} = height of the ground water table [m]

The non-steady state groundwater flow occurs in response to the changing water table height given by:

$$\frac{dh_{wtbl}}{dt} = \frac{w_{rchrg,sh} - Q_{gw}}{800 \cdot \mu} \quad (\text{Equation 5.15})$$

where

$\frac{dh_{wtbl}}{dt}$ = rate of change in water table height [mm/day]

$w_{rchrg,sh}$ = recharge of shallow aquifer on the i th day [mm]

Q_{gw} = groundwater flow into the main channel on the i th day [mm]

μ = specific yield of the (shallow) aquifer [m/m]

Assuming the linear relationship between the Q_{gw} and h_{wtbl} given in Equation 5.14 holds, and integrating Equation 5.15, we get the following equation:

$$Q_{gw,i} = \begin{cases} Q_{gw,i-1} \exp[-\alpha_{gw} \cdot \Delta t] + w_{rchrg,sh} \cdot (1 - \exp[-\alpha_{gw} \cdot \Delta t]), & aq_{sh} > aq_{shthr,q} \\ 0, & aq_{sh} \leq aq_{shthr,q} \end{cases} \quad (\text{Equation 5.16})$$

where

$Q_{gw,i}$ = groundwater contribution to streamflow on day i [mm]

$Q_{gw,i-1}$ = groundwater contribution to streamflow on day $i-1$ [mm]

α_{gw} = baseflow recession constant = $10 \cdot K_{sat} / \mu \cdot L_{gw}^2$

Δt = time step (1 day)

$w_{rchrg,sh}$ = recharge entering shallow aquifer on i th day [mm]

aq_{sh} = water stored in shallow aquifer at the beginning of day i [mm]

$aq_{shthr,q}$ = threshold water level in shallow aquifer for groundwater contribution to streamflow to occur [mm]

5.9 Results and Discussion

The 'Base' scenario was crucial because the simulated discharge at the Punpun basin outlet could be compared with the observed discharge measurements from the Sripalpur CWC gauge station. This comparison is given in Figure 5.13.

Figure 5.13: Simulated and Observed discharge at Sripalpur outlet of Punpun basin before calibration

The model was accurate for a large period of the modeling, with the simulated discharge following the observed discharge patterns, with the exception of the peak discharge values. Model calibration was carried out using Sequential Uncertainty Fitting Version 2 (SUFI-2) interfaced with SWAT using the SWAT Calibration and Uncertainty Procedures (SWAT-CUP) program. The parameters used in calibration were:

- Curve Number (CN): CN is a function of land use, soil's permeability and antecedent soil conditions (Neitsch et al. 2011).
- Soil available water storage capacity (AWC): AWC is the soil available water capacity [mm H₂O], which is the difference of the field capacity and the water content at permanent wilting point (Neitsch et al. 2011).

1000 calibration runs were carried out for each parameter, and it was observed that the new parameters obtained did not improve the model predictions substantially. Since the focus of the study was not to model the particular river basin most accurately using the SWAT model but to simulate a *Parthenium* invasion in a river basin representative of real world conditions, further calibration was not carried out.

5.9.1 Average Annual Water Balance

Before analyzing each component of the water balance for all the three groups of scenarios at a seasonal scale, it was necessary to observe if the water balance at a yearly scale shifted with changing *Parthenium* cover within a single group of scenarios, and also if there were any changes from one group of scenarios to another.

There are a few choices for checking the water balance of any simulation, depending on the choice of system and corresponding definitions of flows and storages. The variables used to check the water balance for all the three groups of scenarios are given in Table 5.4.

Table 5.4: Average Annual Basin Variables used for Water Balance (Values in brackets are expressed as percentage of respective BASE values)

Variable	Description	BASE	S1	S2	S3	D-BASE	D-S1	D-S2	D-S3	W-BASE	W-S1	W-S2	W-S3
PCP	Average precipitation for the simulation (mm)	867.1	867.1	867.4	867.1	703.2	703.2	703.2	703.2	1140.1	1140.1	1140.1	1140.1
SurfQ	Surface water discharge for the simulation (mm)	221.52	226.79 (102.4%)	226.38 (102.2%)	225.83 (101.9%)	150.35	153.52 (102.1%)	154 (102.4%)	153 (101.8)	389.74	397.2 (101.9%)	397.5 (102%)	396.6 (101.8%)
LatQ	Lateral flow contribution to streamflow during the simulation (mm)	1.73	1.67 (96.5%)	1.76 (101.7%)	1.71 (98.8%)	1.3	1.29 (99.2%)	1.32 (101.5%)	1.31 (101.5%)	2.2	2.17 (98.6%)	2.22 (100.9%)	2.21 (100.5%)
GWQ	Groundwater flow contributing to the streamflow during the simulation (mm)	170.14	167.47 (98.4%)	167.1 (98.2%)	168.58 (99.1%)	126.7	124.26 (98.1%)	124.9 (98.6%)	124.72 (98.4%)	264.71	258.39 (97.6%)	259.36 (98%)	259.96 (98.2%)
WYLD	Total water yield to stream flow during simulation (mm)	388.39	390.59 (100.6%)	390.87 (100.6%)	390.12 (100.4%)	274.2	247.87 (90.4%)	276.14 (100.7%)	273.78 (99.8%)	650.31	651.36 (100.2%)	653.58 (100.5%)	651.47 (100.2%)
ET	Actual Evapotranspiration during simulation (mm)	459.8	457.8 (99.6%)	457.9 (99.6%)	458.3 (99.7%)	417.9	417.8 (100%)	416.4 (99.6%)	418.9 (100.2%)	465	464.5 (99.9%)	462.2 (99.4%)	464.4 (99.9%)
REVAP	Water moving from shallow aquifer to soil profile during simulation (mm)	10.16	10.07 (99.1%)	10.03 (98.7%)	10.08 (99.2%)	9.3	9.16 (98.5%)	9.19 (98.8%)	9.16 (98.5%)	12.73	12.58 (98.8%)	12.54 (98.5%)	12.48 (98%)
DEEP AQ	Deep Aquifer Recharge during simulation (mm)	9.49	9.34 (98.5%)	9.32 (98.2%)	9.4 (99.1%)	7.15	7.02 (98.2%)	7.05 (98.6%)	7.04 (98.5%)	14.6	14.26 (97.7%)	14.31 (98%)	14.33 (98.2%)
TOT AQ	Total water entering both aquifers (deep and shallow) during simulation (mm)	189.78	186.89 (98.2%)	186.46 (98.3%)	188.07 (99.1%)	143.07	140.34 (98.1%)	141.05 (98.6%)	140.83 (98.4%)	291.95	285.13 (97.7%)	286.12 (98%)	286.69 (98.2%)
PERC	Water percolating from soil into the shallow aquifer during simulation (mm)	184.76	181.52 (107%)	182.07 (98.5%)	182.04 (98.5%)	139.26	136.48 (98%)	137.81 (99%)	136.32 (97.9%)	286.24	279.35 (97.6%)	281.24 (98.3%)	279.98 (97.8%)
TLOSS	Tributary channel transmission losses during simulation (mm)	4.99	5.34 (107%)	4.37 (87.6%)	6 (120.2%)	4.15	4.2 (101.2%)	3.58 (86.3%)	4.85 (116.9)	6.34	6.4 (100.9%)	5.5 (86.8%)	7.33 (115.6%)

Water Balance Checks

The average annual water balance checks used in this study are:

- Checking the Total Water Balance:

The ground surface was used as a boundary and soil layers and the shallow aquifer were considered together so that fluxes between them did not need to be accounted. The following water balance equation considered the left hand side (LHS) variables as inflows, and the right hand side (RHS) variables as outflows:

$$PCP = WYLD + ET + DEEP AQ + TLOSS \quad (\text{Equation 5.17})$$

This equation was used for each scenario across the groups of scenarios, and the water balance was acceptable with a maximum of 0.9% error (annual water balance expressed as percentage of annual rainfall).

- Checking water balance of the Soil Layer:

Using the soil layer as the system, the following water balance was conducted. The inflows were represented on the LHS and outflows represented on the RHS:

$$PCP = SurfQ + LatQ + ET + PERC \quad (\text{Equation 5.18})$$

This equation was used for each scenario across the groups of scenarios, and the water balance was acceptable with a maximum of 0.8% error (annual water balance expressed as percentage of annual rainfall).

- Checking water balance of the Groundwater Aquifer system:

Taking the shallow and deep aquifer storages as the system, all the fluxes were considered in the following water balance equation:

$$TOT\ AQ = GWQ + REVAP + DEEP\ AQ \quad (\text{Equation 5.19})$$

This equation was used for each scenario across the groups of scenarios, and the water balance was acceptable with a maximum of 0.4% error (annual water balance expressed as percentage of annual rainfall).

Water Balance within the same group of scenarios

It was found that when average annual water balance components within a single group of scenarios (for instance W-BASE, W-S1, W-S2 and W-S3) were compared, the increase of *Parthenium* cover on the watershed did not have any substantial effect on their relative contribution to water balance. A comparison of the average annual water balance components is given in Table 5.5.

Table 5.5: Comparison of Average Annual Water balance components (as % of average yearly precipitation)

	BASE	S1	S2	S3	D-BASE	D-S1	D-S2	D-S3	W-BASE	W-S1	W-S2	W-S3
SurfQ	221.52 (26%)	226.79 (26%)	226.38 (26%)	225.83 (26%)	150.35 (21%)	153.52 (22%)	153.51 (22%)	152.6 (22%)	389.74 (35%)	397.19 (35%)	397.49 (35%)	396.63 (35%)
LatQ	1.73 (0%)	1.67 (0%)	1.76 (0%)	1.71 (0%)	1.3 (0%)	1.29 (0%)	1.32 (0%)	1.31 (0%)	2.2 (0%)	2.17 (0%)	2.22 (0%)	2.21 (0%)
GWQ	170.14 (20%)	167.47 (20%)	167.1 (20%)	168.58 (20%)	126.71 (18%)	124.26 (18%)	124.9 (18%)	124.72 (18%)	264.71 (23%)	258.39 (23%)	259.36 (23%)	259.96 (23%)
ET	459.8 (53%)	457.8 (53%)	457.9 (53%)	458.3 (53%)	417.9 (60%)	417.8 (59%)	416.4 (59%)	418.9 (59%)	465 (41%)	464.5 (41%)	462.2 (41%)	464.4 (41%)
DEEP AQ	9.49 (1%)	9.34 (1%)	9.32 (1%)	9.4 (1%)	7.15 (1%)	7.02 (1%)	7.05 (1%)	7.04 (1%)	14.6 (1%)	14.26 (1%)	14.31 (1%)	14.33 (1%)

Within any particular group of scenarios, no component of the water balance changes substantially with increasing *Parthenium* cover, as can be inferred by the similar percentages in Table 5.5.

Water Balance across groups of scenarios

A comparison of the average annual water balance components compared across groups of scenarios is shown in Figure 5.14.

Figure 5.14: Water Balance components (expressed in percentage of total water balance) compared across scenario groups, arranged in order of increasing avg. annual rainfall

A simple observation leads to the inference that as average annual rainfall increases, higher surface runoff and groundwater runoff contributions occur, at the cost of a decreasing ET contribution, all expressed as a percentage of the total water balance. Lateral flow and deep aquifer recharge do not seem to vary across the scenario groups.

This was corroborated by analyzing the methods used by SWAT to generate the respective components of water balance.

Using Equation 5.2 it could be inferred that an increase in average annual precipitation leads increasing annual surface runoff. Hence there is a significant increase in the surface runoff contribution to the water balance as the average annual rainfall increases from the Dry period to the Normal and Wet periods.

The decrease in ET contribution with increasing rainfall is a natural consequence to maintain the water balance, and although the percentage of ET contribution decreases from 59% to 41% from the Dry to Wet period, the absolute contribution actually increases. Water stress and temperature stress have additional effects on plant water uptake and soil evaporation, which are discussed in detail in the next section.

Groundwater flow is calculated as a function of the groundwater recharge and the water table height. Groundwater recharge is higher in the case of a higher average annual rainfall and the water table height depends on the groundwater flow itself.

After analyzing the average annual water balance, the expected changes in the contributions by the individual components of water balance, due to variations in average annual rainfall, were observed and could be explained, but the annual water balance within a particular rainfall condition (or group of scenarios) did not change substantially. This warranted a deeper analysis into the each group of scenarios, to understand how the water balance components were affected by land cover changes intra-annually.

5.9.2 Normal Period (1990-1999)

The surface runoff, soil water content and evapotranspiration were observed along with the rainfall, for all the scenarios BASE, S1, S2 and S3.

Common Intra Annual Trends

A few common trends were observed in BASE, S1, S2 and S3.

Surface runoff (in cumecs) increased as precipitation increased (Equation 5.2). Surface runoff is generated whenever the rate of application of water (which includes both precipitation and irrigation) is more than the rate of infiltration (Neitsch et al. 2011). Hence after an initial slow increase (May-June), surface runoff peaked simultaneously with the peak of the monsoon. The surface runoff patterns observed are given in Figure 5.15 and Figure 5.16.

Soil moisture content (in mm/month) also showed generally similar trends to follow the rainfall received by the watershed. It peaked along with or just after the peak of the monsoon, since SWAT incorporates a delay term while calculating percolation into the soil layers. It reached a minimum value around April-May, just before the onset of the monsoon. The soil moisture patterns are shown in Figure 5.17 and Figure 5.18.

ET followed the very similar trends as soil moisture content, but with a lag. ET showed two peaks during the year. The major peak was around the peak of the monsoon, because of the higher amount of rainfall received, and thus more water available in the watershed for evaporation. The other peak was around March every year. This could be explained by the increased plant growth as modeled by SWAT and this leading to more plant water uptake from the soil layers and subsequently more ET from the watershed.

Figure 5.15: Simulated Surface Runoff (1992 - 1995)

Figure 5.16: Simulated Surface Runoff (1996-1999)

Figure 5.17: Simulated Soil Moisture Content (1992-1995)

Figure 5.18: Simulated Soil Moisture Content (1996-1999)

Figure 5.19: Simulated Evapotranspiration (1992-1995)

Figure 5.20: Simulated Evapotranspiration (1996-1999)

Differences in Trends: Intra-Annual Effect of *Parthenium* Invasion

The common responses shown by the water balance variables in all the scenarios, however, differed from each other in the extent to which the same variables responded. A typical year, 1996, is chosen to explain these differences. The year 1996 is chosen because it experienced a rainfall of 840.4 mm, which is closest to the average of the entire modeling period (1990-1999), and the responses are representative of the other modeled years.

The surface runoff is plotted in Figure 5.21.

Figure 5.21: Simulated Surface Runoff (1996)

The increment in surface runoff was highest for S3, followed by S2, S1 and the BASE condition. This could be explained by the difference in curve numbers (CNs) of the land cover. A higher curve number implies a higher runoff potential while a lower curve number indicates a lower runoff potential. The CNs chosen for AGRL (Agricultural Row Generic – the most common land cover in BASE) and PRTH (*Parthenium* – the most common land

cover in S3) are given in Table 5.6. The CNs for AGRL were set by default in SWAT, and the CNs for PRTH were the chosen to be the same as that of Barren Land available in SWAT.

Table 5.6: SCS Curve Numbers for AGRL and PRTH land covers

Land Use	Hydrologic Soil Group			
	A	B	C	D
AGRL	67	77	83	87
PRTH	77	86	91	94

The soil moisture for the same year follows an interesting trend during the earlier part of the year, where there is a sharp decrease in soil moisture during February and March, before it starts increasing for all scenarios during June after the onset of the monsoon. This fall is sharpest in BASE and is least for S3. This is explained together with the ET observations. The simulated soil moisture for 1996 is given in Figure 5.22.

It is interesting to analyse the soil moisture and the ET together, because although the PET is not a function of soil moisture, the actual ET takes into account the soil moisture conditions, particularly during dry soil moisture conditions.

The monsoon ET trends have been explained already, and BASE, S1, S2 and S3 respond similarly during the Wet period. In the dry season, the ET trends are in lagged consistency with the trends of soil moisture. The initial sudden decrease in soil moisture is accompanied by a sharp increase in ET, and this increase is highest in BASE (corresponding to the largest fall in soil moisture in BASE). Since in S3, *Parthenium* had saved the soil moisture initially, there is a point at which the ET values cross each other and the trend is reversed,

with S3 followed by S2, S1 and BASE, although it should be made clear that at this point, all the ET values are decreasing. In the absence of rainfall, the ET dependency on soil moisture is enhanced, and the consistent decrease in soil moisture decreasing in this period may have led to this decrease in ET. The ET trends are given in Figure 5.23.

Figure 5.22: Simulated Soil Moisture (1996)

Figure 5.23: Simulated Evapotranspiration (1996)

5.9.3 Dry Period (1966-1970)

The simulations which were run for the dry period of 1966-1970 yielded results similar to the Normal period simulations.

There were almost no differences between the variations of the D-BASE, D-S1, D-S2 and D-S3 in the water yield parameter (which is the sum total of surface runoff, lateral flow, and groundwater flow).

Soil moisture content also followed trends similar to those in the Normal Period, peaking around the peak of the monsoon, after having reached their yearly minimum just before the onset of monsoon. The differences between the D-BASE, D-S1, D-S2 and D-S3 scenarios were similar to the differences between BASE, S1, S2 and S3, which have been explained in the previous section. The soil moisture content for the simulation of the Dry period is given in Figure 5.22.

ET also followed trends similar to the Normal period. There were two maxima every year in the Dry period simulations as well, along with the lag from the soil moisture content. The trends followed by the different scenarios observed in the Normal period, were observed here as well. The ET for the Dry period is plotted in Figure 5.23.

Figure 5.24: Simulated Soil Moisture Content (Dry Period)

Figure 5.25: Simulated Evapotranspiration (Dry Period)

5.9.4 Wet Period (1984 – 1988)

The Wet period scenario also yielded similar results when compared to both the Normal and the Dry periods. However, the magnitudes of all the flows were much larger as compared to either of the previous scenarios because of the inherently higher rainfall.

Similar to both the previous cases, the soil moisture content peaked with the peaking monsoon season, and was very low just before the onset of the monsoons. More water was held as soil moisture in the *Parthenium* infested condition (W-S3) as compared to the W-BASE condition from March onwards, and this excess soil moisture released through the *Parthenium* as transpiration, with an added delay of about a month, resulted in a slightly higher value of the increasing W-S3 ET when compared to the decreasing ET values for the other cases.

The soil moisture content and evapotranspiration for these scenarios are plotted in Figure 5.24 and Figure 5.25 respectively.

Figure 5.26: Simulated Soil Moisture (Wet Period)

Figure 5.27: Simulated Evapotranspiration (Wet Period)

5.10 Limitations of the SWAT Study

The limitations of the study undertaken using the SWAT model are as follows:

- The parameters of the plant growth were approximated due to the lack of physiological and bio-chemical parameter measurements of *Parthenium*.
- More detailed parameters related to irrigation, fertilizer application on the crops, and pesticide application and harvest operations (done by farmers on the field) on *Parthenium* (if used) could not be incorporated on account of lack of specific data on management practices.
- Multiple germinations of *Parthenium*, which is very common in the physical world, were not included in the SWAT modeling, leading to only one season of *Parthenium* being modeled per year.
- No chemical/biological parameters of *Parthenium* were analysed due to the lack of input data on such parameters.

Chapter 6

Summary and Concluding Remarks

The work done can be summarized as follows:

1. Phytometer experiments were carried out to compare transpiration losses of *Parthenium* with Bermuda grass, which was selected as a reference grass.
2. A MATLAB code was developed to simulate the evapotranspiration losses of *Parthenium* using the Penman-Monteith Method. Both winter stands and summer stands were computed separately, and compared with a winter (*rabi*) agricultural crop (wheat) and a summer (*kharif*) crop (maize).
3. The SWAT model was used to model the effect of an invasion by *Parthenium hysterophorus* on water balance components of the Punpun river basin, for separate periods of normal, lower and higher than average annual rainfall conditions.

The conclusions that can be drawn from this study are:

1. *Parthenium hysterophorus* weed has less ET losses when compared to the wheat and maize crops, using the ASCE Penman-Monteith Method, on account of its lesser stomatal conductance and higher surface resistance.
2. SWAT modeling also re-establishes that *Parthenium* has a lower ET losses in non-stressed soil conditions. But it also reveals that an area infested with *Parthenium* weed has a reduced tendency to lose soil moisture as compared to an area with agricultural crop cover, especially when the soil is drying. This leads to higher ET

of *Parthenium* as compared to agricultural crop cover, just before the onset of monsoons.

3. The effect of *Parthenium* invasion on surface discharge and groundwater recharge is not significant at a basin scale.

Chapter 7

Future Scope

Phytometer experiments:

- More control on the environmental conditions – temperature, humidity, solar radiation and (if possible) CO₂ concentration is needed for more reliable inferences from experimental study about transpiration trends of *Parthenium*, as compared to other reference grasses.
- It should be ensured that the plants under experiment are not under water stress at any point of time, which could not be ascertained in this study.
- Other agricultural crops, which are invaded by *Parthenium* should also be included in the transpiration studies, for direct comparisons under the same conditions.
- Randomized experiments using a lysimeter inside a greenhouse with controls on environmental variables can yield experimental data to reliably test the hypothesis posed in the thesis.

Detailed SWAT Modeling:

- Many parameters used in the SWAT model were not known hence their values were assumed which induced uncertainty in SWAT results. The future studies should aim on measuring these parameters under controlled conditions so that the parameteric uncertainty, which is the major source of uncertainty in SWAT model, can be reduced.

Modelling the effect on water quality variables:

- Since *Parthenium hysterophorus* leaches lactones and phenols into the soil, there is a definite possibility of adverse effects on the soil health due to these harmful chemicals. These need to be investigated, and quantified.
- Such a study is vital as *Parthenium* may have long term damaging effects on soil health, and that is especially important in an agriculturally dependent economy such as ours.
- A study of this sort will require careful bio-chemical laboratory experiments to determine the chemical composition of the residue of *P.hysterophorus*.
- Nitrogen and Phosphorus stress needs to be explored in the context of *Parthenium*, and studies are to be undertaken to measure N-yield and P-yield for the same.
- A suitable model would have to be chosen which would be able to predict the effect of a *Parthenium* invasion on the bio-chemical composition of the soil of the area which it invades.

To develop strategies for mitigating the effect of *Parthenium* on the hydrology of a river basin, *Parthenium* needs to be treated like an agricultural crop and less like a weed for research studies. This means that the rigors that are involved in undertaking a thorough analysis of an agricultural crop should be applied to *Parthenium hysterophorus* also, so as to overcome our current lack of understanding of its hydrological impacts.

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Appendix

MATLAB Code for Penman Monteith Evapotranspiration Calculation

```
% CALCULATION OF ET USING THE ASCE PENMAN MONETEITH METHOD (Monteith 1965, 1981)

% Assumptions:
% 1. For the psychrometric constant, Height of Weather station = Height of Kanpur (Above mean sea level) =
126m [Wikipedia]
% 2. This is for winter => LAI = 3.49 (from October-December 1996 and 1997 seasons according to [2])

% Getting input data
[T_Max] = xlsread('input_data.xlsm', 'Data', 'B30:B105');           % Max daily temp
[T_Min] = xlsread('input_data.xlsm', 'Data', 'C30:C105');           % Min daily temp
[RH_Max] = xlsread('input_data.xlsm', 'Data', 'D30:D105');
% Max daily rel humidity
[RH_Min] = xlsread('input_data.xlsm', 'Data', 'E30:E105');
% Min daily rel humidity
[Uz] = xlsread('input_data.xlsm', 'Data', 'F30:F105');
% Component averaged Wind speed at the height of z=10 metres [1]
[T] = xlsread('input_data.xlsm', 'Data', 'G30:G105');               % Mean daily temp
[RH] = xlsread('input_data.xlsm', 'Data', 'H30:H105');             % Mean daily RH
[ea] = xlsread('input_data.xlsm', 'Data', 'I30:I105');             % Mean daily Actual Vapour pressure (ea)

% For Aerodynamic resistance (ra), applied for neutral stability conditions
Zw = 10;

% Height(m) of wind speed measurements in any standardised AWS
Zh = 10;                    % Height(m) of humidity/air temp measurements
h = 0.152;                  % Mean height(m) of vegetation (WINTER) [2]
d = 0.67*h;                 % Zero plane displacement height(m)
Zom = 0.123*h;              % Roughness length(m) governing momentum transfer
Zoh = 0.0123*h;            % Roughness length(m) for transfer of heat and vapor
vk = 0.41;                  % von Karman's constant

[ra] = zeros(76,1);
for k=1:76
```

```

    ra(k) = (log((Zw - d)/Zom) * log((Zh - d)/Zoh)) / ((vk)^2 * Uz(k));
end

% For slope of Saturation Vap. Pr. vs temperature curve
[D] = zeros(76,1);
for k=1:76
    D(k) = 2503 * exp (17.27*T (k)/(T(k)+237.3)) / (T(k)+237.3)^2;
end

% For Saturation Vapor pressure
[es] = zeros(76,1);
for k = 1:76
    es(k) = ((0.6108 * exp(17.27*T_Max (k)/(T_Max(k)+237.3))) + (0.6108 * exp(17.27*T_Min
(k)/(T_Min(k)+237.3)))) / 2;
% [e(T_Max) + e(T_Min)]/2
end

% For Bulk surface resistance (rs)
LAI = 3.49;

% Leaf Area Index (m2 of leaf per m2 of soil surface) (Winter Oct-Dec Avg)
LAI_act = 0.5*LAI;

% Radiation absorbed only by top-half of the canopy [3] but this is ignored, as LICOR LAI2000 measures SLAI
(Silhouette leaf area index) which should be ~ One sided leaf area (OLAI)

[rl] = zeros(76,1);
for k=1:76
    rl(k) = 170.833;

% Bulk stomatal resistance [s-1 m] of well-illuminated leaf

[rs] = zeros(76,1);
for k=1:76
    rs(k) = rl (k) / LAI;

```

```

end

% Latent heat of Vapourisation
[l] = zeros(76,1);
for k=1:76
    l(k) = 2.501 - (2.361*(10^(-3)))*T(k);           % lambda (Latent heat of vaporisation, in MJ/kg) [5]
end

% For Psychrometric constant (g)
[P] = zeros(76,1);
[g] = zeros(76,1);
for k = 1:76
    H = 136;                                       % of weather station(m), above elevation at
    reference level (126+10)
    P(k) = 101.3 * (1-(0.0065*H/(273.16+T(k))))^(5.26); % Atmospheric pressure
    g(k) = 0.000665*P(k);                         % Psychrometric constant
end

% Wind adjustment not necessary as the ASCE equation uses incorporates
% actual wind measurements at actual height for computing ET % For Extra terrestrial radiation (Ra)
[Dm] = xlsread('input_data.xlsm', 'Data', 'K30:K105'); % Date of the month
[M] = xlsread('input_data.xlsm', 'Data', 'L30:L105'); % Month number
[Y] = xlsread('input_data.xlsm', 'Data', 'M30:M105'); % Year number

[J] = zeros(76,1);
[o] = zeros(76,1);
[dr] = zeros(76,1);
[Ws] = zeros(76,1);
[Ra] = zeros(76,1);

for k=1:76
    J(k) = Dm(k) - 32 + floor(275*M(k)/9) + 2*floor(3/(M(k)+1)) + floor((M(k)/100) - (mod(Y(k),4)/4) +
0.975);
    o(k) = 0.409 * sin((2*pi*J(k)/365) - 1.39);
    dr(k) = 1 + 0.033*cos(2*pi*J(k)/365);
    Ws(k) = acos(-1*tan(26.3*pi/180)*tan(o(k))); % Latitude = 26.3 degrees = 26.3*pi/180 radian
    Ra(k) = 24/pi * 4.92 * dr(k) * (Ws(k)*sin(26.3*pi/180)*sin(o(k)) +
cos(26.3*pi/180)*cos(o(k))*sin(Ws(k)));
end

```

```

end
% For Radiation data (ESTIMATING USING HARGREAVES SAMANI METHOD FOR TEMPERATURES)

[Rs] = zeros(76,1);
Krs = 0.19; % For interior locations, where RH is not affected by water body
for k = 1:76
    Rs(k) = Krs * ((T_Max(k) - T_Min(k))^0.5) * Ra(k);
end

[Rns] = zeros(76,1);
[Rnl] = zeros(76,1);
[Rso] = zeros(76,1);
[fcd] = zeros(76,1);
[Rn] = zeros(76,1);
for k=1:76
    alpha = 0.23; % Taking albedo constant at 0.23
    Rns(k) = (1-alpha)*Rs(k); % Shortwave radiation

    % For longwave radiation
    Rso(k) = (0.75 + 2*(10^(-5))*136) * Ra(k); % 136 = elevation of station above sea level = 126m + 10m
    fcd(k) = 1.35*Rs(k)/Rso(k) - 0.35;
    sigma = 4.901*(10^(-9)); % Boltzmann constant in MJ/K4/m2/d
    Rnl(k) = sigma/2 * fcd(k) * (0.34 - (0.14*((ea(k)^0.5)))) * ((T_Max(k)+273.16)^4 +
(T_Min(k)+273.16)^4);

    % For net radiation
    Rn(k) = Rns(k) - Rnl(k);
end

[ET] = zeros(76,1);
% Calculating ET
Kt = 86400; % Conversion constant (in sec/d)
Cp = 1.013 * (10^(-3)); % Specific heat of air at constant pressure (MJ/kg/degree)
[G] = zeros(76,1); % Can be ignored at daily time step
for k=1:76
    ET(k) = ((D(k).*(Rn(k)-G(k))) + Kt*d*Cp*(es(k)-ea(k))./ra(k)) / (1(k).*(D(k) + g(k).*(1+(rs
(k)./ra(k))))); % For Daily Time step, and Tall reference ET (~0.5m)

```

```
end
% Cn=1600, Cd=0.38

% REFERENCES
% [1] Guide to Meteorological Instruments and Methods of Observation, WMO, 2008)
% [2] D.K.Pandey et al; Growth, Reproduction, and Photosynthesis of Ragweed Parthenium
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% [3] Allen, R. G., M. Smith, A. Perrier, and L. S. Pereira. 1994a. An
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% Allen, R. G., M. Smith, L. S. Pereira, and A. Perrier. 1994b. An update
% for the calculation of reference evapotranspiration. ICID Bulletin 43(2):35-92.
% [4] http://www.staff.uni-giessen.de/~gh1461/plapada/stomata/stomata.html Körner C, Scheel JA, Bauer H,
1979. Maximum leaf diffusive conductance in vascular plants. Photosynthetica 13, 45-82.)
% values in mmol/m2/s to be divided by 41 (calculation based on 293K and 105Pa)
% [5] Harrison, L.P. 1963. Fundamentals concepts and definitions relating to humidity. In Wexler, A. (Ed.)
Humidity and moisture. Vol 3, Reinhold Publishing Co., New York, NY, USA.
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